

**AN ASSESSMENT OF ROOF TOP WIND
RESOURCES AND ITS OPTIMUM
UTILIZATION USING ROOF
INTRGRATED WIND TURBINES IN
DUBLIN**

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Abstract

In past decades, numerous localities have attempted to harness wind resources for electricity generation using rooftop micro-scale wind turbines. Disappointingly, the monitored capacity performance of various roof-integrated wind turbines (RIWTs) is typically only 5%-11% of the designed capacity. This low capacity factor makes them uneconomical. To improve the performance of these turbines, a more rigorous modeling approach has been developed for a selected site within Dublin, Ireland. As part of this investigation, the meteorological wind data were analyzed and sub-scaled for use with a detailed computational model generated from a terrestrial laser scanned point cloud. The wind flow field at the site was simulated using computational fluid dynamics in a commercial finite volume program, through which an optimum turbine location on the roof top was found. The outcomes of such an approach demonstrate that the capacity factor for RIWTs varies significantly with its seating position. The power output can be as low as zero at randomly installed position. The optimum location for electrical power can be estimated before its placement which will subsequently increase the economic feasibility of RIWTs in urban areas.

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“A calm sea doesn’t make a skilled sailor”

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Abbreviations and Symbols

3-D- 3 Dimensional

ABL- Atmospheric Boundary Layer

AD-Anderson Darling statistic

ANOVA-ANalysis Of VAriance

BWT-Built-environment Wind Turbine

CFD- Computational Fluid Dynamics

CLM-Cyclone Client license Manager

CT-Carbon Trust tool

DEM-Digital Elevation Model

DSM-Digital Surface Model

EU- European Union

GIS- Geographic Information System

LIDAR-LIght Detection And Ranging

LOD- Levels Of Detail

MFR- Multiple Frames of Reference

MIT-Massachusetts Institute of Technology

ML-Maximum Likelihood

NLSB- National Land Survey Board

NOABL- Numerical Objective Analysis of Atmospheric Boundary Layer

NREL- National Renewable Energy Laboratory

RANS - Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations

RR-Roebuck Castle Student Residence

RIWT- Roof Integrated Wind Turbine

RMB- Right Mouse Button

Rps- Rotations per second

SEAI-Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland

TI- Turbulence Intensity

TSR- Tip Speed Ratio

UCD- University College Dublin

UK- United Kingdom

WAsP- Wind Atlas and Application Program

WMO- World Meteorological Organization

Wind Turbine Index:

A - Rotor swept area (m^2)

ρ - Air density ($1.225kg/m^3$)

P - Power (W)

C_p -Power coefficient (dimensionless)

C_{pmax} - Maximum power coefficient (dimensionless)

λ - Tip Speed Ratio (-)

σ – Standard deviation of the wind data

u_{avg} - Mean wind speed (m/s)

Meteorological and Geometric Index:

π - Pi (3.14)

z_d - Displacement height (m)

z_o -Roughness length (m)

$U(z)$ - Mean wind speed profile (m/s)

u^* -Friction velocity (m/s)

k -Von Karman constant having a value of 0.41(-)

$f(U)$ - Probability of observed wind speed U (-)

k - Weibull shape factor (-)

c – Weibull scale factor (m/s)

z_{avg} -Mean height of obstacles (m)

Z_b - Blending height (m)

Z_{avg} – Average height of the buildings (m)

U_m -Mesowind speed (m/s)

U -Mean wind speed (m/s)

d - Street width (m)

h - Building height (m)

Chapter 1: Introduction

The prolonged use of fossil fuels will eventually lead to their depletion, as well as the affiliated degradation of the environment. Hence, interest continues to rise in renewable energies. For example, the European Union (EU) renewable energy directive 2009/28/EC highlights the vital role wind plays in achieving Europe's renewable energy targets. One component of this is likely to be Roof-Integrated Wind Turbines (RIWTs). While RIWTs are gaining popularity in domestic electricity micro-generation, there is a wide gap between the promised output by the manufacturer and the electricity obtained by the user. One reason for this is the absence of reliable wind resource information for the exact RIWT installation at the location (Walker, S.L., 2011). The other reason is the lack of technical guidelines available for the installation of these turbines. A recent report of National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) discusses the role these RIWTs can play in achieving the green energy targets.

Ireland has abundance of wind resource; still a major portion of the electricity is generated using the fossil fuels. It is due to the fact that the installation of off-shore wind turbines requires a huge investment and effective electricity transmission system shares a big part of that cost. Therefore RIWT can be a feasible option for electricity generation in urban areas of Ireland. There is not much information available regarding the use of RIWT in Irish wind climate. This work is first and foremost in terms of analyzing Dublin's wind resource for its suitability for micro-generation using RIWT.

1.1. Objectives of the work:

The objectives of the work are to study and analyze the following questions:

1. Are the areas in Greater Dublin suitable for RIWT installations?
2. How the wind characteristics at the site can be estimated using the nearest meteorological station data?
3. What are the benefits of using terrestrial laser scanned point cloud data for generating a computational model?
4. How urban wind resources can be evaluated using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD)?

5. How to optimize the turbine placement location over the roof top?

1.2. Outline of the work:

The work started with an extensive literature review, which is presented in chapter 2. It gives the basic concepts of wind flow, wind power generation; additionally it discusses the use of CFD for evaluating the wind resource at a site and various case studies presenting the interaction of wind turbines with the built environment and their results. Chapter 3 describes the methodology adopted to estimate the roof top wind resource at the selected site equipped with a weather station. A computational model for the site has been generated and statistical analysis of meteorological wind data has been carried to derive the input parameters for simulating the wind flow at the site using CFD. The steps taken for simulating the flow in complex urban terrain and generating the model of a wind turbine for obtaining the power curve inside ANSYS CFX has been explained. The results obtained using the methodology explained earlier are presented in chapter 4. Chapter 5 discusses the significance of the obtained results and also compares the obtained CFD results with the past works. Chapter 6 states the outcomes of the study as contribution to the RIWT's state of art along with the limitation and suggestions for the future work.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1. Introduction:

The literature overview explains the concepts and the research conducted in the field of roof integrated wind turbines (RIWTs). This chapter explains the basic laws governing the wind flow for the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) and the principles of wind based electricity generation. According to the European wind atlas, several European cities have significant wind resource that can be used for the micro-electricity generation as an alternative to fossil fuels to reduce the carbon emission. But urban areas are characterized by the presence of dense man-made structures (blunt bodies) leading to impinging, separation and vortex shedding making the wind flow at the relevant elevations very complex and indeterminate between the building canopies. Thus accurate estimation of wind resources is extremely challenging. Also presented herein are the approaches used by the researchers to predict the urban wind resource and specific studies related to RIWTs.

2.2. Wind in the Atmospheric Boundary Layer:

Atmospheric Boundary Layer is the lowest layer of the atmosphere and is characterized by the turbulence exchange of heat, mass and momentum at the ground surface. The wind speed drops to zero in accordance with the no slip condition on this surface. For the estimation of wind energy in the ABL, the wind is estimated to be neutral (temperature effects are neglected) and only the mechanical turbulence is considered.

According to Prandtl (1904), the ABL flow can be separated into two regions of equal shear stress, the outer and inner region. Equating the velocity gradient for both regions results into a wind profile that varies logarithmically as a function of the height above the ground. This function also depends on the foot prints of the surface (also known as aerodynamic parameters) over which the wind is blowing as shown in equation 2.1.

$$U(z) = \frac{u_*}{k} \ln\left(\frac{z-z_d}{z_0}\right) \quad (2.1)$$

Where u^* is the friction velocity also known as shear velocity (m/s) that characterizes the shear stress at the surface, k is the Von Karman constant having a value of 0.41, z_d is the displacement height (m) and z_o is the roughness length (m). The displacement height and the roughness length are the aerodynamic parameters in the above equation. Displacement height is the average height where momentum is absorbed by the canopy (Raupach, 1994). Roughness length is that height where the wind velocity drops down to zero following the logarithmic law.

2.2.1 Estimation of Aerodynamic parameters (z_d and z_o):

The aerodynamic parameters are estimated using either the morphometric or micro-meteorological approach as described below:

- a. Morphometric approach:** In this method, a spatially-continuous database of the surface obstacle (surface roughness) geometry is sub-scaled and used inside a wind tunnel to calculate the aerodynamic parameters. It was found that the shape, size density and distribution of these parameters affect the wind profile.

Calculation of aerodynamic parameter is done using one of the approaches:

- a) In the height based approach, based on the numerical and experimental results on the building and its surroundings, techniques are employed to establish the aerodynamic parameters in terms of the mean height of the obstacles z_{avg} .

$$z_d = f_d z_{avg} \quad (2.2)$$

$$z_o = f_o z_{avg} \quad (2.3)$$

Table 2.1: The different values of f_d and f_o used in the calculation of z_d and z_o mentioned by Grimmond and Oke (1998)

Researcher	f_d	f_o	Surface type
Garratt (1992)	0.67	0.10	All land surfaces
Raupach et al. (1991)	0.64	0.13	Field crops
Raupach et al. (1991)	0.8	0.06	Forest
Hanna et al (1992)	0.5	0.1	Urban areas

b) The parameters were also calculated by using the height and the plan aerial fraction. (Kutzbach, 1961), (Counihan, 1971).

c) Raupach (1992) used the frontal area index with mean height for the estimation of displacement height and surface roughness.

b. Micrometeorological approach: This approach experimentally observes the wind speed in the field at different horizontal and vertical locations and uses the logarithmic wind velocity (equation 2.1) to calculate the aerodynamic parameters by solving the logarithmic equation iteratively.

Wieringa (1980) used the following analogies for the micrometeorological approach:

1. The wind speed at an elevation of 60m for an area of $5 \times 5 \text{ km}^2$ doesn't change much in horizontal direction, albeit of the change in the surface roughness. This height of 60 m was defined as blending height (Z_b), the wind speed at this height is called as Mesowind speed (U_m). The logarithmic law is used to calculate U_m using the wind station's data (at an elevation of 10m, with a roughness of open terrain 0.003m obtained from table 2.2). The estimated U_m value was used with the Davenport roughness classification to calculate the wind speed at the location of interest. The approach followed used the roughness values based on land use pattern summarized as given in the table 2.2. Here x is a typical upwind obstacle and H the height of the corresponding major obstacles. For class 7; the applicability of logarithmic exposure correction modeling is doubtful and requires at any rate the substitution of $(z-d)$ for z in the formulae, where d is the displacement length ($d \sim 0.7 \times \text{average obstacle height}$). Class 8 is analytically intractable and can better be modeled in a wind tunnel (Wieringa, 1980).

Table 2.2: Roughness Values adapted from Davenport (1960) in z_0 form by Wieringa(1980)

Class	Terrain Description	z_0
1	Open sea, fetch at least 5km	0.0002
2	Mud flats, snow; no vegetation, no obstacles	0.005
3	Open flat terrain, grass; few isolated obstacles	0.03
4	Low crops; occasional large obstacles, $x/H > 20$	0.1
5	High crops; scattered obstacles, $15 < x/H < 20$	0.25
6	Parkland, bushes; numerous obstacles, $x/H \sim 10$	0.5
7	Regular large obstacle coverage (suburb, forest)	1
8	City centre with high and low rise buildings	unknown

2.3. Wind Energy fundamentals:

The amount of useful power generated by a wind turbine using the kinetic energy available in the wind is given by the well-known equation:

$$P = \frac{1}{2} C_p \rho A U^3 \quad (2.4)$$

Where P is the power (W), C_p is the power coefficient, A is the rotor swept area (m^2), ρ is the air density (1.225 kg/m^3), and U is the mean wind speed (m/s). Extracting 100% of the kinetic energy of the wind is impossible, as this would require the wind to instantaneously stop upon encountering the turbine's swept area. Thus, only a fraction of the power in the wind is captured by a turbine, and the power co-efficient C_p accounts for this (Burton, 2001). Burton (2001) showed that the theoretical limit value of C_p also known as Betz limit is 0.593. The typical value of C_{pmax} lies in the range of 0.35-0.5 (Eriksson et al., 2008).

Values of turbine power coefficients vary not only between different turbines but are also based on turbine's operating conditions, most notably the tip speed ratio (TSR or λ), which is the ratio of turbine blades tip velocity to the incoming wind speed. The variation of TSR with power coefficient is shown in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the relationship between a generic wind turbine power coefficient and tip speed ratio.

The power in the wind is proportional to the cube of the wind speed (equation 2.4). Thus, minor inaccuracies in predicting the wind speed at a potential turbine site can result in significant errors in estimated energy yields. As the wind varies both temporally and spatially, using a representative value in terms of mean wind speed as used in equation 2.4 is inadvisable. Furthermore, as the exact estimation of wind variability over time is difficult, a probabilistic approach is better to predict the wind speed variation. The Weibull probability distribution function has been shown to be representative of the variation in hourly mean wind data from several wind station datasets. The Weibull distribution function for a given wind velocity is given by Weisser (2003).

$$f(U) = \left(\frac{k}{c}\right) * \left(\frac{U}{c}\right)^{(k-1)} * e^{-\left(\frac{U}{c}\right)^k} \quad (2.5)$$

Where $f(U)$ is the probability of observed wind speed U , k (dimensionless) is the Weibull shape factor, and c (m/s) is the Weibull scale factor.

The figure 2.2 shows the diurnal variation of the wind in Grenada, West Indies.

Figure 2.2: Diurnal Weibull probability distribution function plotted (Weisser, 2003)

The power curve of the wind turbine is obtained using the relation between power and wind speed, the Betz limit and the relation between turbine efficiency and TSR. The expected power output of the turbine is indicated by the power curve of the wind turbine as function of the incoming wind speed. By multiplying the output from the Weibull distribution function with the power curve, we can calculate the expected energy yield of the wind turbine installed at the desired locations can be calculated.

2.4. Wind resource assessment in urban areas:

The estimation of the wind resource present at a site is the most important determining factor that helps in estimating the viability of a potential turbine installation. The accuracy of the expected energy yield of the wind turbine installed depends upon the accuracy of the wind conditions predicted at the site. There are a number of different approaches for the assessment of wind resource in urban areas. With respect to urban sites, the methods employed for assessing the wind resource normally ignore the effects of local surface features which in turn lead to the generation of error while calculating the wind energy. Thus, hybrid approaches combining detailed analytical and computational techniques are increasingly being used by the research

community. The common approaches that have been used for the wind resource assessment are explained in brief below:

2.4.1. Direct measurement approach:

Initially measurements over long periods of time was the most common approach for assessing RIWTs as the same was being done in case of wind farm site assessments. However the small-scale nature of installations made this uneconomical, hence shorter time periods were used from which a longer time scale was extrapolated (Landberg et al., 2003). Unfortunately this approach proved to be costly and unreliable.

2.4.2. Analytical approach:

The analytical approach typically follows the wind atlas methodology (i.e., physical models used to translate measurements from one location to estimate those at another location for predicting the wind resource). This approach uses a long-term dataset of wind measurements from a local reference site to estimate the available wind resource by considering the local topography and the surrounding surface roughness. However, it neglects the effects of nearby obstructions at the potential turbine installation location, which can compromise the accuracy of the estimate of potential.

2.4.3. Computational Fluid Dynamics approach:

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) helps in eliminating the issues faced by the analytical approach by simulating the flow field around a specific arrangement of surface obstructions and solving for the specific geometric conditions using the Navier-Stokes equation which is the fundamental equation of motion governing the fluid flow.

As an example Kalmikov et al (2010) used the state of art CFD along with the local wind measurements to predict the long-term wind climatology inside of Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) campus in Cambridge. The wind velocity has been measured at the two sites

inside the campus using anemometer and four months data has been used to calculate the power density at the site which has been parameterized by the Weibull probability function. This estimated power has been used to validate the CFD simulated power. The results showed good agreement at the site measurements.

Notably still CFD cannot be used exclusively as a standalone tool for the analysis but its integration with the real time measurements decreases the cost and time giving a sufficiently reliable result.

Precise analysis of flow field around the buildings is difficult using CFD because of the complexity of urban flow properties (Murakami, 1998). Effective CFD analysis generates a high computational cost as it requires a fine grid resolution. And the application of the wall law to the flow field with separation does not give satisfactory results. Also the computational resources required for this approach were usually prohibitive for small-scale wind site assessments and restricted its use to relatively small local areas, less than 10km^2 (Xie and Castro, 2009). Murakami (1998) also found that nonetheless, CFD continues to be highly valuable for evaluating simpler, spatially-averaged flow models for use in urban areas. Further details of the required CFD modeling is presented in section 2.5.

2.4.4. Hybrid approach:

For a more reliable wind resource assessment a significant research has been undertaken to combine the CFD approach and the analytical approaches available to develop new modern hybrid approaches.

One of the oldest hybrid approaches created an atlas, which used homogenous topography and land use description for the vertical and horizontal extrapolation of wind data (Hillring et al., 1998). The wind atlas data set was generated by applying standard conditions to the time series data from different meteorological station. The available formula of the wind power (equation 2.4) was combined with the frequency distributions of wind speed to calculate the value of

available mean energy at the site. As an example, Hillring (1998) used wind atlas analysis and application program (WAsP), the analysis and application was performed as shown below:

Analysis: Meteorological wind data + site description = Wind atlas data

Application: Wind atlas data + site description = Estimated wind climate

The analysis was done with the topographical information obtained from the National Land Survey Board's (NLSB) land use data (only four land use pattern water, open, forest, urban area). The methodology underestimated the energy density in the areas of high elevation (by 10% to 20%) and overestimated the values in low-lying areas.

Another interesting example of wind data base system is Numerical Objective Analysis of Atmospheric Boundary Layer (NOABL). The data base was created by mass control flow model (interpolating the 56 weather station data for a 10 year period). This method considers the effect of surface roughness, but due to the imitated representation of surface roughness, the values obtained for urban areas are not with high precision. An improvement over the NOABL database is made by using the Carbon Trust (CT) wind speed estimator, which accounts for the surface characteristic over which the flow occurs.

A study conducted by Drew et al. (2013) used internal boundary layer propagation at an urban neighborhood scale. This concept is based on the fact that when the wind flow encounters a sudden change in land use pattern it adjusts itself to the new surface roughness forming an internal boundary layer. It was observed that the derived displacement height decreased with distance from the city center. Based on the turbine's output power curve the annual energy production was estimated for various small wind turbines at different locations using Weibull probability density function. The wind speed was calculated at an elevation of 5m above the building roof and 10m above the ground. The results were validated against the existing techniques. NOABL showed 27% overestimation of wind energy. Carbon Trust tool had underestimated the wind speed by 17 %.

Recently, Hopkins et.al (2013) predicted the mean wind speed as a function of height for a number of UK cities, and the results matched with the measured values. Their methodology used

the Numerical Objective Analysis of Boundary layer (NOABL) database for the wind speed. The aerodynamic parameters were calculated by dividing the city into number of square grids and the z_o and z_d values were assigned to each grid. The wind speed at 10m above the ground was scaled up to the height of urban boundary layer and then scaled down to the blending height using logarithmic wind profile (equation 2.1). The figure 2.4 shows the schematic diagram of the methodology implemented by Hopkins et al.

Figure 2.4: Schematic Diagram of methodology implemented (Hopkins et al., 2013).

2.5 Model generation for Computational simulation:

CFD can be an efficient along with the meteorological stations wind data (which is widely available across the world) for estimation the wind resource at any specific site. A robust computational analysis requires a geometrically detailed model and accurate input parameters.

2.5.1. Technologies used for the generation of computational models:

There is a huge demand for high quality three-dimensional surface models for studying the urban environment and its dynamics. The creation of 3D urban models represents a real challenge, considering the short time for the creation of the models and the relative unavailability of detailed geospatial data. As each operation is unique, there is no *one-unique-solution* that can be applied. Numerous methods and algorithms for the 2D and 3D reconstruction of building models using various sources have been reported in the literature.

2.5.2. Input data types for model:

The availability of an accurate geospatial data has a direct impact on the quality of a given 3D urban model. At least, two types of datasets are required to create an urban 3D model: a) elevation or terrain data and b) 2D vector datasets featuring minimally the building footprints on the ground with their heights or elevation. McClune (2014) described the different data acquisition methods namely photogrammetry, airborne laser scanning or human-based interpretation and digitization to describe the topography of an urban environment. These methods can be broadly classified as a) model-driven and b) data-driven. Model-driven approaches tend to reconstruct only simple roof types such as flat, ridged or hipped since they fit only pre-determined roof models to the data. The data-driven approaches use the extracted data in order to create a roof model and hence tend to be more flexible. But both the methods are dependent on the underlying data and features extracted from the data.

Images are perhaps the most obvious input source for 3D modeling as they are very easy to obtain, to store, and to exchange. Nowadays, many images depicting urban sites are being taken, uploaded and exchanged over the internet worldwide. This information has been used as a valuable source for large-scale urban reconstruction (Snavely N et al., 2010). However, imagery is inherently a 2D source of extremely high resolution and density, but view depended and lacking depth information (Liebowitz et al., 1999).

The successful use of aerial and satellite imagery (that was restricted to the professional sector of photogrammetry and remote sensing community for many years) for reconstruction became possible due to the advances of Web-mapping projects, like Google Maps and Bing Maps (Vanegas C.A et al.,2010).

Another type of input that is excellently suitable for urban reconstruction is LIDAR data. LIDAR (LIght Detection And Ranging) is a technique that uses light impulsion (in the form of a laser ray) to calculate the distance between the light emitter and a given object that reflects the light pulse to the emitter, to deliver semi-dense 3D point clouds which are very precise, especially for long distance acquisition. In other words, it typically utilizes laser light, which is projected onto

surfaces and it is reflected backscattering is captured, where structure is determined through the time-of-flight principle (Campbell J, 2011). Many modern algorithms rely on input from LIDAR, both terrestrial and aerial.

Both the data types explained above provides a source for varying Levels Of Detail (LOD) as they can be acquired from the ground or from the air. According to the predefined standard (OpenGIS) for urban reconstruction LODs proposed by the photogrammetry community (Groger.G et al., 2008), airborne data is more suitable for coarse building models reconstruction, ground based data is more useful for individual buildings and façade details.

2.5.3 Input data to 3D model:

Generally three main approaches are being used for the generation of 3-D models. They are as follows: a) conventional techniques such as Vector Map data, Digital Elevation Model (DEM), Aerial images etc., b) the second approach is based on high resolution satellite images with LASER scanning; c) the final approach uses terrestrial images by using Close Range Photogrammetry with Digital Surface Model (DSM) & Texture mapping. (Surendra Pal Singh et al., 2013).

It is generally difficult to reconstruct a reliable 3D model from conventional techniques alone because of the inaccurate reconstruction of the object height (Baillard et al., 1999). Moreover, the image dissimilarities, concealed areas, shadows, height discontinuities and discrepancies between smooth terrain and man-made features hamper the 3D reconstruction from 2D imagery (Tack, Frederik et al., 2012). However in the present scenario, due to the advancement of techniques and algorithms, real time web based photo-textured, scalable and accurate 3D modeling is possible. The techniques use single input data type or multiple-input data type for the reconstruction of 3D models.

For example, dense aerial LASER scanning data was used to derive the necessary geometric parameters for the different models developed by various researchers (Kutzbach, 1961, Counihan, 1971, Lettau, 1969, McDonald et al, 1998, Raupach, 1994), that calculated the

aerodynamic surface roughness length (Holland et al., 2008). The methodology used LIDAR data independently for deriving the geometrical information of the building and trees. The data set was preprocessed for the extraction of building and trees based on continuity assumption. Buildings were detected as solid objects and the trees being porous obstacle, the leaf area index was used to calculate the resistance to wind. The model excluded the objects smaller than 2.5 meters in height with surface area less than or equal to 6m^2 .

A multi-input method was proposed by Zebedin et al. (2008), which involved combining aerial imagery with additional information from DEMs. They introduced an algorithm for building reconstruction combining sparse line features and dense depth data with a global optimization algorithm based on graph cuts (Kolmogorov.V, 2004). Their method also allowed generating multiple LODs of the geometry.

An interesting approach using multiple input data type was followed by integrating LASER scanning and imagery technique to generate a reliable 3D model to overcome the difficulty in extracting the building and roof edges from point cloud because of the unavailability of sharp boundaries in the point density (Huang, 2011). Another technique for massive reconstruction from images and LIDAR was introduced by Poullis and You (2011). Their method based on a statistical analysis of the geometric properties of the data, automatically created lightweight, watertight polygonal 3D models from airborne LIDAR.

As presented above, there is no one-unique-solution for the creation and exploitation of 3D urban models. The availability of a broad range of methods to exploit the foundation datasets to create reliable 3D models makes the task of selecting a viable method very difficult and interesting.

2.6 Various case studies for building integrated wind turbines and their results:

Mertens (2003) used CFD simulation for the prediction of wind speed at roof tops by considering all the local effects of the surface roughness created due to the presence of surrounding built environment. The logarithmic wind velocity profile was used, and the aerodynamic parameters were obtained using micrometeorological approach. The Weibull probability distribution was

used for overall wind direction on the rooftop. The results showed flow separation at the roof edge and it was observed that the velocity vector at the rooftop was not parallel to the horizontal axis. Instead, it was making an angle with the horizontal known as the skew angle. The angularity showed variation with specific roof position, the shape of the building and the surrounding roughness. The performance of the horizontal axis RIWT varied with the skew angle. The edge, corner and center of the roof were selected for the reference wind speed. The simulation results were analyzed for the two main criterions of low turbulence and high velocity and the roof centre identified as the optimum placement location with the highest energy density.

Simon Watson et al. (2007) refined the methodology of Mertens for predicting the performance of RIWTs in urban environment by using wind atlas normalized to the standard reference conditions to estimate the mean wind speed. An initial correction for local building geometries was applied to calculate the temporally and spatially averaged wind profile in the target area. CFD was used to model the flow as it passed through different arrays of simple houses. The wind speed at potential turbine mounting positions was factored with an estimated the Weibull distribution function and the turbine power curve were used to estimate the electrical yield and the capacity factor. The established result indicated that that a high mean annual wind speed did not alone account for a good turbine location as the incident wind profile and speed-change factor varied with local conditions, relative wind direction, house type, and alignment. All these factors critically impacted turbine viability. The results concluded that the effects of different building types and layouts were quite significant for RIWT positional optimization. When the wind was parallel to the ridgeline, house shape was the most important factor. But the building stagger factor dominated when the wind was perpendicular to the ridgeline. The influence strongly depended on the building shape and wind direction and to a lesser extent to stagger and spacing.

As the roof top of high rise buildings have better wind resource compared to the low rise buildings, a number of typical building models have been tested inside a wind tunnel, and the wind measurement has been carried at different roof location (Blackmore 2008). The results were validated against the field measurements. All the measurements were for the two wind direction, parallel and perpendicular. The measured mean wind speed was normalized by the

local reference wind speed, it is the speed measured without the models in position. The ratio of the mean wind velocity to the local reference wind velocity was estimated. For some of the building estimated ratio was greater than 1 which meant that at some locations on the roof the mean wind profile is accelerated (more than the usual) resulting into an increased wind velocity. The result presented gives one more analogy to consider the micro generation using RIWTs.

After investigating that the presence of high-rise building in some cases (depending on their orientation and the flow direction) increase the wind velocity, work has been carried out to see the effect of different roof shapes namely pitched, pyramidal and flat (Ledo et al, 2011) on the wind velocity and the turbulence intensity. Turbulence intensity depended highly on the roof shape and the wind direction. The flat roof top has higher wind velocity and lower turbulence intensity in comparison to the pitched and pyramidal roof type and it was found that the power density above the flat roof was greater and more consistent than the other roof types. The summary of the result is shown in tabular form

Table 2.3: Recommendation for turbine mounting on different roof types in suburban setting (Ledo et al, 2011).

	Corner	Edge	Centre
Pitched roof	✓	x	x
Flat roof	✓	✓	✓
Pyramidal roof	✓	x	x

To understand the effect of building shape in amplifying the wind turbulence kinetic energy, studies has been carried by Khayrullina(2013) using simple parallel rectangular building blocks to assess the wind energy potential in passages between parallel buildings. This work highlighted the influence of the aerodynamic roughness length and wind direction on the wind speed distribution within passages as shown in Figure (4). Another significant finding was that the

power output was highly shown to be dependent on building geometry and the turbine type. Small RIWTs to the corner or the side of a building took advantage of the favorable flow between buildings. The analysis of the wind flow field indicated that large streets with an aspect ratio, $d/h > 1.5$ (d = street width, h = building height) were characterized by higher wind speeds and were thus the most suitable locations for the installation of micro-wind turbines.

a): Setup Overview

b) Orientation of buildings in prevailing wind direction

c) Positioning of wind turbines depending on passage width

Figure 2.5: Work done by Khayrullina(2013)

Islam Abohela (2011), presented the results of CFD simulations of flow patterns, turbulence intensities and stream wise velocities above six different roof shapes: flat, domed, gabled,

pyramidal, vaulted and wedged roof which represented the most commonly used roof shapes in urban areas. The results from this work set the guidelines for positioning wind turbines above the investigated roof shapes under different wind directions. The most important result of this work was that the vaulted roof was found to be the optimum roof shape for roof mounted wind turbines as the integrated wind turbine yielded 56% more electricity than a freestanding wind turbine in the same location under the same flow conditions while the wedged roof had the least accelerating effect on wind above it.

Figure 2.6: Different Investigated Roof Shapes and Location of measurements and Wind directions by Abohela (2011)

Figure 2.7: Flow above a vaulted roof by Abohela(2012)

Numerical simulations have been carried out to investigate the behavior of a horizontal axis wind turbine as a function of building depth, width and height, as well as wind turbine position, height and wind speed. Milanese et. al. (2012) carried this simulation and used the Taguchi method and the Variance analysis (ANOVA) to assess the correlation of these parameters with the turbine output and the most significantly effecting parameter were the height at which the turbine is located. The optimal turbine was about 20% of the total building depth.

Abohela (2012) has given an insight regarding the influence of roof shape, building height and site location on wind speed. They found that the presence of the building within the free stream caused two affects; the first was an acceleration of the stream wise velocities around the building and the second was the increase in the turbulence intensity in the vicinity of the building. The greater the free stream velocities, the greater was the potential to extract useful power from the micro turbine but the increase in turbulence intensity decreased the turbine efficiency. Hence both the parameters should to be considered when positioning the turbine.

Dymock and Dance (2013) explained the importance of securing an optimum site location for a wind turbine to extract the maximum power from undisturbed flow of air. Based on their findings they stated that the lowest point of the wind turbine's swept area should, ideally, be at least 9-15 meters above the tallest object around within 152 meters radius. However, the local topography of rooftops, tall structures and long, winding streets caused unpredictable, irregular flow, high wind shear and a complex turbulent flow as well as acceleration across rooftops and tunneling and venturi effects at ground level affecting the flow of wind.

2.7. Summary:

The literature presented above summarizes that the performance of roof integrated wind turbines varies significantly from one location to another. The effects of different building types and layouts are quite significant and attention must be paid to these details in order to find the best mounting position. The wind resource in urban settings is highly site-specific and less predictable hence a detailed analysis is needed for any site. The following chapters explore these issues for an actual site.

Chapter 3: Scope and Methodology

3.1. Scope:

Currently 16.3% of Ireland's electricity is produced from wind with a 2020 target of 37% (Renewable energy in Ireland 2012). Most of this come from the offshore wind farms located on Ireland's west coast, as onshore wind turbines face strong planning permission objections. Roof Integrated Wind Turbines (RIWTs) offer an alternative, yet they are rare in Ireland, even in Dublin where a disproportionate amount of the country's energy is consumed. Therefore a pilot study was conducted for evaluating the wind climate of Dublin and its suitability for micro generation in Greater Dublin.

3.2. Methodology:

The meteorological time series wind data from Met Eireann meteorological stations were analyzed to assess the available wind resource in Outer Dublin and Greater Dublin. Additionally, the aerodynamic parameters for the site were determined as a necessary input parameter for the computational model. A geometrically detailed model of the building and its surroundings was generated using a three dimensional point cloud generated from Lieca P20. The computational simulation was carried using ANSYS.15 to estimate the wind velocity at different locations within the site. To estimate the maximum achievable power at these locations, a basic model of a micro-scale turbine having a diameter of 400mm was generated using DesignModeler in ANSYS. The turbine performance was simulated for the site specific wind conditions to obtain the power curve and the maximum power output at the site. Finally the maximum achievable capacity factor at the site was calculated. The flow chart for the adopted approach is presented in figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Flow chart showing the methodology adopted for the study

3.3. Site Selection:

The building selected for the study was Roebuck Castle Student Residence (RR), located inside the University College Dublin (UCD) main campus close to the Owenstown park entrance. It is a six storey building having an area of 660m² and a total height of 19.6m, equipped with a roof top weather station. The hourly wind data-set is recorded and stored using a pro-net data acquisition system.

Figure 3.2: A view of Roebuck Residence with Anemometer installed on the roof top

3.4 Generation of the detailed geometrical model:

In the absence of CAD drawing and with an intention of having identical geometry for computational modeling as the existing geometry, A terrestrial light detecting and ranging device(LIDAR) Leica P20 has been used to scan the site in the form of point cloud. The details of the steps are explained below.

3.4.1. Laser Scanning:

To create an accurate geometrical model of the building, a Leica P20 terrestrial laser scanner was used to scan the building at the site. The scanning process was carried out in two phases, in accordance with the handbook provided by Leica Cyclone (Leica Cyclone Handbook, 2013).

Figure 3.3: Leica P20 Laser Scanner

Phase 1: The first phase of scanning was done at the ground level using 15 stations to record the full extent of the building facades with three target points recorded at each station. Each station generated a point cloud of a portion of the building façade. The reference points were recorded to aid in the registration of the individual point clouds. The point clouds were analyzed, registered and merged into a full 3-Dimensional model using Cyclone 9.1.

Phase 2: The scanner was placed on the roof of Roebuck Residence (RR) and the roof was scanned along with all the adjacent structures in the vicinity within a radius of 120m (maximum range of the scanner) using 6 stations. Again a series of reference points were recorded to aid in post processing as above.

3.4.2. Generation of the 3-D model from the point cloud:

Step 1: Once the scanned data was collected, it was imported into the computer using **Interface software called Cyclone (version 9.1)**. A project named Roebuck Complete was created. Two data bases titled Roebuck Building and Roebuck Roof were created within the project. The phase 1 scanned data was stored in Roebuck Building and the second phase scanned data was stored in Roebuck Roof. All the scans were registered into Cyclone.

Step 2: For obtaining a single scan from each project all the scans were registered using a single coordinate system, by the common objects overlapping in the scans. Three manual constraints were used to avoid the error. “*Preview*” command was used to ensure visually that there was no error and the constraints were exact. Once the registration was correct, a single model space view for the scans was chosen and “*freeze registration*” option was selected to avoid any further changes. The same process was repeated for the other data base. The unwanted points from the point cloud were deleted by creating fences to obtain a good quality of point cloud data.

Figure 3.4: Model view spaces created from the Roebuck building databases

Figure 3.5: Model view spaces obtained from the Roebuck roof

Figure 3.6: Combined 3D point cloud of the site

Both the model spaces were combined to obtain a three dimensional point cloud of the site as shown in figure 3.6.

3.4.3. Generation of the solid model:

Software named ‘CloudWorx’, a plug-in for AutoCAD was used to import the 3D point cloud into AutoCAD 15.0.1. This software is supported by the Cyclone Client license Manager (CLM). The main objective of the model was to acquire the building orientation and geometry in a realistic manner. Once the 3-D point cloud was imported into AutoCAD, CloudWorx basic AutoCAD commands and poly lines were used to accurately trace the external building walls and the plan of the site. The height of each building was obtained by opening the model spaces and using the “*measure*” tool within Cyclone to measure the distance between the ground and the roof top. The two dimensional plan of each building was converted into a solid model by using the “*extrude*” command. Since the buildings were not on the same ground level, an uneven three dimensional surface was created by connecting the base of each building as shown in figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: Three dimensional site model of obtained using AUTOCAD

3.5. Analysis of meteorological wind data:

There are two fully equipped meteorological stations in Dublin area. One is at the Dublin airport, ($53^{\circ}25'34.39''$ N, $6^{\circ}15'33.70''$ W) and is situated on a flat, open land sloping away gradually on the east side towards the coast 8 km away. The other is the Casement aerodrome ($53^{\circ}18'20''$ N, $6^{\circ}26'20''$ W), which is 16 km away from the case study site towards the south of Dublin city. The two meteorological stations with the site location are shown in figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8: Location of the two meteorological stations and the site under study

3.5.1. Estimation of wind profiles at the weather stations:

To plot the logarithmic wind profile at any location, the value of shear velocity, also known as friction velocity (U^*) is required. This is used to characterize the shear stress on the surface of boundary. For the study of atmospheric physics its value is assumed to be constant. The value of U^* at the Dublin airport was calculated using the time series wind data obtained at an elevation of 10m. The airport is surrounded by a thick grass cover with no built environment nearby. The value of z_0 was estimated using Oke's roughness classification as shown in table 2.2. The standard value of z_0 for the Dublin airport is 0.03. The formula for U^* was derived from the log law (equation 2.1) applied to the hourly values in the time series data set available as a Microsoft excel sheet. A sample of the data sheet used in the calculation is shown in table 3.1 below. After the estimation of U^* , the wind velocity at different elevation was estimated and the wind profile was plotted. For plotting the wind profile at the Casement aerodrome, the same set of shear velocity values were used as the shear velocity is constant for the whole city.

Table 3.1: A sample of the data sheet used in the calculation of U*

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
Year	Month	Date	Hour	Wind Spee	Direction	U*	U*/K	5mtrs	15mtrs	20mtrs	30mtrs
2012	1	1	0	19	230	1.30809	3.27022	16.7435	20.3081	21.2565	22.5972
2012	1	1	1	20	230	1.37694	3.44234	17.6248	21.3769	22.3752	23.7866
2012	1	1	2	17	220	1.1704	2.92599	14.9811	18.1704	19.0189	20.2186
2012	1	1	3	18	220	1.23924	3.09811	15.8623	19.2392	20.1377	21.4079
2012	1	1	4	16	230	1.10155	2.75387	14.0998	17.1015	17.9002	19.0293
2012	1	1	5	15	230	1.0327	2.58176	13.2186	16.0327	16.7814	17.8399
2012	1	1	6	12	230	0.82616	2.0654	10.5749	12.8262	13.4251	14.2719
2012	1	1	7	10	270	0.68847	1.72117	8.81239	10.6885	11.1876	11.8933
2012	1	1	8	10	230	0.68847	1.72117	8.81239	10.6885	11.1876	11.8933
2012	1	1	9	11	230	0.75731	1.89329	9.69363	11.7573	12.3064	13.0826
2012	1	1	10	13	220	0.89501	2.23752	11.4561	13.895	14.5439	15.4613

3.5.2. Estimation of wind profiles at the selected site:

The value of aerodynamic parameters was required for plotting the logarithmic wind profile at the site using the data from the meteorological station available at the site. The value of these parameters depends on the dimensional features (area, height) of the structures resting on the ground. A classification table given by Oke was used for the initial estimation of the parameters. In order to use the classification table, the average height of the buildings at the area of interest was required. For simplicity, in this study only a small rectangular area (tile) in the close vicinity of the site was selected, which had a similar dimension of the computational domain (section 3.6) as shown below.

Figure 3.9: The selected area of study in yellow and environs selected in red

The average building height within the tile was found using Google earth in-built tool, visual inspection (photographs taken from the rooftop), and terrestrial scans. Since the height of the buildings in the area was not uniform, the weighted mean of the height was estimated using equation 3.1.

$$Z_h = \frac{(A1 \times h1) + (A2 \times h2)}{(A1 + A2)} \quad (3.1)$$

Z_h is the average height of the buildings in the tile, A1 (80%) is the area covered by the building having an average height of 10m (h1), A2 (20%) is the area covered by the buildings having an average height 19-20m (h2). Most of the buildings shown in the tile were residential units having an average height of 9-10m, while the buildings in the yellow square had an average height of 19-20m. The average height of the buildings obtained in the tile was 12 meters. The table provided by Grimmond and Oke is shown below.

Table 3.2: Typical aerodynamic properties of homogenous urban areas given by Grimmond and Oke (1998)

Urban surface form	Z_h (m)	Z_d	Z_o	g_{am}	C_d
Low height and density Residential-one and two storey single houses, gardens, small trees. Mixed houses and small shops. Warehouse, light industrial, few trees	5-8	2-4	0.3-0.8	30-50	0.6-1.0
Medium height and density Residential-two and three storey large or closely spaced, semidetached and row houses, large trees. Less than five storey blocks of flats with open surroundings. Mixed-houses with shops, light industry, churches, schools.	7-14	3.5-8.0	0.7-1.5	45-75	0.9-1.5
Tall and high density Residential-closely spaced<six-storey row and block buildings or major facilities, town center	11-20	7-15	0.8-1.5	50-80	1.0-1.6
High-rise Urban core or suburban nodes with multistory tower blocks in dense urban surroundings. Major institutional complexes	>20	>12	>2.0	>90	>1.9

The wind velocity changes as the wind enters the city due to the wind interaction with the surface terrain (Wieranga, 1986). Thus, the use of such raw meteorological data may not be reflective for an urban location and direct measurements may be time intensive and costly. In contrast CFD simulation can be used to generate reliable results. In order to obtain these results through CFD a systematic approach is required as discussed in the previous section.

Table 3.2 represents the values in a range; thus selecting a single value within the range needed proper care. The value of $z_o(1.0m)$ and $z_d(7m)$ selected from the table after a number of iterations to increase the accuracy, together with the shear velocity estimated earlier was used in equation 2.1 to plot the logarithmic wind profile at the site.

Additionally, the time series wind data obtained from the roof top weather station was substituted in equation 2.1 to calculate the aerodynamic parameters. The anemometer was placed at a height of 21.6 m above the ground, z_d value was taken as two third of the RR height (Weireinga,1980) and z_o value was calculated using logarithmic equation from the hourly data set. The estimated z_o value was used to extrapolate the velocity at different height to obtain the mean wind profile.

The profile obtained from the Oke's roughness classification was compared against the profile obtained from weather station data and the closest value of z_o and z_d was found to be 1.8 m and 8 m respectively.

3.5.3. Directional analysis of the wind:

The distribution of wind speed and direction at a particular location is important for selecting the inlet of the computational domain; it is obtained by a wind rose plot. The frequency of winds over a period of time is plotted by the wind direction with color bands showing wind ranges using a polar coordinate system of Girding (Wikipedia). The plot shows the frequency of winds blowing from a particular direction over a specified period. The plot typically uses 16 cardinal directions as shown, although they may be subdivided into as many as 32 directions (Theon Bill, 2011).

Figure 3.10: Directions in a typical wind rose plot (Source: Internet)

Open source software called WRPLOT View from Lakes Environmental was used for the generation of wind rose plot for the meteorological data collected for this work. **WRPLOT View** is a wind rose program that provides visual wind rose plots and the frequency analysis of the obtained plots. The excel data file was imported into the software to generate the **.sam** file for creating the wind rose plot.

3.5.4. Analysis of wind variability:

Wind velocity in the atmospheric boundary layer is inconsistent and unsteady, thus from energy point of view it was very important to quantify the variation of the wind. To estimate the yearly variation of the wind a statistical software package called MINITAB was used. All the wind speed data for two years (2012 & 2013) were imported to the Minitab work sheet and the task bar options were selected as shown below.

Start >> quality tool >> individual distribution identification

This command gave the result of goodness of fit test to find the best distribution function (the function with lowest Anderson Darling (AD) statistic and a probability (P) value less than 0.005). The result for the Dublin airport data obtained is as shown below. It also provided the values of the parameters on which the fitting function depended.

Distribution	AD	P
Normal	134.048	<0.005
3-Parameter Lognormal	35.421	*
2-Parameter Exponential	1973.091	<0.010
3-Parameter Weibull	33.138	<0.005
Smallest Extreme Value	607.561	<0.010
Largest Extreme Value	44.059	<0.010
3-Parameter Gamma	32.017	*
Logistic	115.572	<0.005
3-Parameter Log logistic	58.682	*

Distribution	Location	Shape	Scale	Threshold
Normal*	10.84223		5.40782	
3-Parameter Lognormal	2.90115		0.28352	-8.09486
2-Parameter Exponential			10.84284	-0.00062
3-Parameter Weibull		2.1200	12.29234	-0.03678
Smallest Extreme Value	13.69415		6.30178	
Largest Extreme Value	8.31129		4.47138	
3-Parameter Gamma		5.68408	2.29406	-2.19738
Logistic	10.49104		3.06448	
3-Parameter Log logistic	2.79540		0.18338	-6.28263

From the worksheet, it was clear that the Weibull distribution function gave a good representation of the variation in the data set. Thus the three parameter (scale parameter, shape parameter, threshold value) Weibull distribution curve was plotted.

3.5.5. Turbulence intensity:

Due to the presence of a dense built environment in the urban boundary layer, the wind velocity changes significantly in both the horizontal and vertical directions, leading to an indeterminate complex phenomenon called turbulence. In a simplified way, turbulence is represented by its statistical property. Turbulence intensity (TI) is one of the widely used statistical descriptor in CFD. Thus the turbulence intensity at the site was calculated using equation 3.2.

$$TI = \frac{\sigma}{u_{avg}} \quad (3.2)$$

where σ is the standard deviation of the wind data used and u_{avg} is the mean wind speed (m/s). For calculating the TI, it was preferable to use the wind observation of 10 minute, hence the 2013 time series 10 minute wind data from the rooftop anemometer was used.

3.6. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation:

CFD is a finite volume program which solves the complex nonlinear partial differential equation governing the fluid flow. For assessing the flow field at a site, the 3D computational model is obtained from the terrestrial laser scanner was imported into ANSYS CFX. A three dimensional computational domain was generated outside the model to account for the influences created by the external nearby surroundings. The domain is defined as a geometrical region over which the computational simulation is performed. The dimensions of the domain were selected in accordance with the best practice guideline for CFD simulation of flows in the urban environment.

The particulars of the domain are highlighted below:

- The dimensions of the vertical extension of the domain was less than or equal to $5H$, where H was the height of building (m).
- The lateral extension of the domain was taken to be greater than or equal to $5H_{\max}$, where H_{\max} was the maximum height of the building (m).
- The longitudinal extension was set to be equal to $5H$ to develop the realistic approach flow entering the domain and equal to at least $10H$ behind the building group so that the flow redevelopment took place behind the wake region.

The steps followed for starting a simulation in CFX simulation are presented below:

Step 1: Starting ANSYS by double clicking, then option was selected from the taskbar to view the drop down menu as shown below.

Figure 3.11: Drop down menu to import the CAD file saved

Step 2: Right click (Right Mouse Button, RMB) on the “*geometry*” option to import the CAD file saved.

RMB >> Geometry >> Import CAD file saved

Step 3: The domain was generated using “*concept*” option. The rectangular cross section was selected around the site in the XY plane, and the domain was extruded to a height of 200m using the “*extrude*” command. This domain height should be ten times the height of the building under study in order to avoid isolate the area understudy from its nearby surrounding. The lateral and longitudinal expansions are six times the building height as shown below:

Figure 3.12: 2D representation of domain created for simulation

Step 4: To solve the partial differential equation, the computational domain was discretized into small volumes to capture the important physical phenomenon. CFX Mesher was used by employing the “*mesh edit*” option to divide the whole domain into small elements. “*Automatic method using polylines*” was used to create the mesh, because the geometry had many sharp edges due to the construction of uneven ground surface below the buildings (connecting the building bases). The mesh size was varied between 1m on the building face 4m for the domain in the whole domain to reduce the computational cost and time. A inflation layer was upto a

height of 2 meters was used on the building roof top to capture the shear and wakes forming around the building as shown below. The buildings at the site was constructed at different times hence the foundation level was different for all the three building group. This foundation unevenness was captured by the terrestrial scanner; hence a base has been constructed using polylines to create a common surface for the buildings. The total number of mesh elements generated was 17216217.

Figure 3.13: Mesh generated in the mesher

Step 5: After generating the required mesh, the different boundaries inside the domain were named by using “*Selection*” and the boundary conditions were set as shown below. These named selections are used for the detailed exploration of wind flow in and around these boundaries in the CFD post process.

Figure 3.14: Selection of different boundaries and inserting name to explore the wind flow in the post process

Step 6: The initial parameters describing the physics of flow were set in CFX-Pre which was solved by CFX solver during the run. The five boundary conditions used are given below:

- A. **Inlet:** The inlet boundary represents the mean upstream wind represented in terms of a mean wind profile and turbulence quantities entering the domain. Details for the K-epsilon model have been discussed by Richard and Hoxly (1999). The boundary condition at the inlet represents the upstream surface roughness characteristics of the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) affecting the wind velocity. The roughness characteristics over a surface depend on the shape, size, density, and distribution of the structures residing over the ground and expressed in terms of a roughness length. The analytical representation of mean wind profile over a surface at different elevation is represented by equation 1. This equation was modified to be used with the logarithmic profile for a K-epsilon turbulence model in CFD, three equations are used to represent the velocity, turbulent kinetic energy(TKE), turbulent eddy dissipation (TED)

$$U(Z) = \frac{U_*}{k} \ln\left(\frac{Z+Z_0}{Z_0}\right) \quad (3.3)$$

$$TKE = \frac{U_*}{\sqrt{C_U}} \quad (3.4)$$

$$TED = \frac{U_*^3}{k(Z+Z_0)} \quad (3.5)$$

Thus, the average height of the buildings obtained in the tile was 13.75 m. The surface roughness value is calculated using the empirical relationship given previously and is found to be

$$Z_0 = 0.08Z_{avg} \quad (3.6)$$

The shear velocity has the effect of a roughness parameter and is assumed to remain constant across an elevation in a neutral atmosphere. Thus, the meteorological station data at the building was used to calculate the velocity. At heights beyond 200 m above the ground the velocity is considered virtually independent of the roughness length (REF), which mean at this height the velocity should be equal at all locations across a city.

$$U_{250m @ met station} = U_{250m @ site} \quad (3.7)$$

At the airport, $Z_0 = 0.03m$ and the u^* value was calculated via equation 3.2, which results in a value of 0.75m/s. Substituting these values into equation 3, the velocity at the airport at an elevation of 250 meters is 16.43m/s.

$$U_{*site} = \frac{U_{250}}{\ln\left(\frac{Z+Z_{0site}}{Z_{0site}}\right)} \quad (3.8)$$

- B. The ground and the building groups were defined as smooth wall with no slip condition. As discussed by Blocken et.al(2007) to solve the shear stress on the walls, Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations (RANS) were used by CFX solver. The wall shear stress was calculated from local velocity gradient normal to the wall.
- C. For achieving a homogenous boundary layer profile inside the domain , the top and the lateral faces were selected as symmetry
- D. The outlet was selected to have a constant static pressure boundary condition.

Step 7: To obtain a reliable convergence high resolution advection scheme with a residual target of 0.00001 was selected as shown in equation

Figure 3.15: Showing the selected boundary condition and solver control setting

Step 8: Once “The run is completed successfully” message appeared on the screen the result section was post process was used to visualize the results. The graphical and numerical results were obtained which is shown in chapter 4.

The performance detail of a micro-wind-turbine is unavailable hence to obtain the power curve a micro wind turbine model was used in the CFX. The details are explained below in form of pictures for a better understanding.

3.7. Wind turbine design and simulation:

3.7.1. Wind turbine model:

At present, there are no published technical details available for the performance of a wind turbine having a diameter less than 500mm. Hence an existing CAD model of the turbine from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) having a diameter of 8.5m was sub-scaled to a diameter of 400mm using ANSYS DesignModeler. The simulation was performed with different ranges of velocity to obtain the power curve, which was further used to estimate the achievable power at the site. Before going to the simulation details, some basics of turbine generation are introduced here:

Theory behind the wind turbines:

Wind turbine is a device for extracting the kinetic energy from the wind. The three main indicators of the turbine performance are power, torque and thrust. Usually for convenience the turbine performance is expressed in terms of non dimensional parameters. The two parameters generally used are the Power coefficient (C_p) and the tip speed ratio (TSR, represented as λ).

$$C_p = \frac{\text{Power extracted by the turbine}}{\text{Power available in the wind}} \quad (3.9)$$

$$\text{TSR, } \lambda = \frac{\text{blade tip speed}}{\text{wind speed}} \quad (3.10)$$

The typical performance curve for a high speed wind turbine is given below:

Figure 3.16: Plot showing the C_p vs λ curve

As seen from the graph the maximum value of power coefficient is at a tip speed ratio of 7. But in case of three blade micro-scale turbine the tip speed ratio varies between 4 and 5.

The value of TSR depends most importantly on the blade geometry, as the blade design details are not known. The TSR values starting from 2.5 were taken and equation 3.3 was solved to get the blade tip speed. The equation showing the relation between blade tip speed and rotations per second (rps) is given below. In the CFX simulation of the turbine this value of rps was used as an input parameter.

$$\text{bladetip speed} = \text{rps} \times \pi \times \text{rotor diameter}(m) \quad (3.11)$$

The process followed in the simulation of a rotating body is complex. Therefore all the steps are explained with the pictures given below.

Step 1: The CAD model of the turbine (diameter=8.5m) with the fluid domain was imported into the ANSYS DesignModeler and sub-scaled to a model having a diameter of 400mm using a scale factor of 0.047058. Additionally two 3D flow domains were created; one for the turbine rotor and the other for the fluid flow analysis and a simulation was carried inside CFX.

Create >> Body transformation >> Scale >> Generate

Figure 3.17: Wire frame of the geometry imported into DesignModeler

The figure above shows the wire frame of the geometry imported into the DesignModeler and the different sections named. Only one blade of a three blade turbine was simulated to simplify the simulation and the torque value obtained from the simulation was multiplied by three for simulating the effect of a three blade turbine. An artificial shroud was created to capture the wakes generated by the turbine during its rotation.

Step 2: The geometry was transferred to the meshing application; the different meshing tools were then applied to resolve the flow gradients.

Step 3: The blade geometry was suppressed

Right Mouse Button (RMB) >> Blade Geometry >> Suppress

Step 4: Coordinate system was inserted.

RMB >> Coordinate systems >> coordinate system >> Geometry >> Select the red line indicated in the figure.

Figure 3.18: Inserting the coordinate system

Step 5: For fixing the match control coordinate system created above was used as the rotation axis.

RMB on mesh >> insert >> match control >> Scope >> Select the faces as shown

Figure 3.19: Fixing the Match control

Step 6: Body sizing was done to obtain more control over the inner most body.

RMB >> Mesh >> Sizing >> the inner most body as shown in figure

Figure 3.20: Body sizing

Step 7: Insert inflation

RMB >> Mesh >> insert >> inflation

Figure 3.21: Inserting inflation

Step 8: Sweep method

RMB >> mesh>> insert method in object tree >> sweep method

Figure 3.22: Sweep Method

Step 9: Sizing for outermost body.

RMB >> mesh >> insert sizing >> select the outermost body as shown.

Figure 3.23: Sizing of outermost body

Step 10: Edge sizing.

RMB >> mesh >> insert sizing >> select the line and settings shown below.

Figure 3.24: Edge sizing

Step 11: Duplicate sizing

RMB Edge sizing >> duplicate sizing

Figure 3.25: Duplicate Edge sizing

Step 12: Duplicate edge sizing for the three edges of the blades with the setting shown below

Figure 3.26: Duplicating the edge size for the remaining edges

This step ends the CFD solver setup for the simulation.

3.7.2. Turbine simulation:

The main goal of next step was to assign the flow domains to the geometries. This simulation consisted of a stationary domain for the outer flow field and a rotating domain for the rotating part. Appropriate physics and boundary conditions were applied to the domain and also the interfaces between the rotating and the stationary domain were set up. Two expressions were defined as monitor points for the force and torque. The generated torque accounted for the total dynamic force transferred to the building and no occupant discomfort condition was assumed while the turbine was running.

The steps followed in CFX-Pre for a run given below:

Step 1: Double click on the CFX set up cell and the mesh generated above will be automatically loaded into the CFX-Pre.

Step 2: Setting the location of the domain, in which the rps value calculated above, was placed for the motion of the domain.

RMB >> Flow analysis >> Insert the domain name “rotor” on the domain rotor panel.

Figure 3.27: Rotor fluid domain setting and properties for a TSR value of 5 and normal velocity of 4 m/s.

Step 3: The outer flow domain was created by repeating the previous steps but the options were set opposite as it is a stationary domain

Figure 3.28: Setting the Outer flow domain

Figure 3.29: Result once the Outer flow domain is set

Step 4: The boundary was selected as shown.

RMB >> outer boundary >> boundary condition >> inflow, the inlet velocity of 4m/s is inserted.

The steps are repeated for outlet, ground.

Step 5: Setting the boundary condition.

RMB >> Object tree >> select the appropriate name for fixing the boundary condition as shown in the following steps.

Figure 3.30: Object tree used for boundary setting conditions in the following steps

Step 6: The boundary condition for hub nose was inserted as shown below.

Figure 3.31: Boundary condition for hub nose

Step 7: The far field boundary conditions were set.

Figure 3.32: Boundary conditions for far field

Step 8: Boundary condition for the blade wall was set as shown.

Figure 3.33: Boundary conditions for blade wall

Step 9: Since one domain was stationary and the other was rotating, 3 Multiple Frames of Reference (MFR) were used to simulate the interfaces between the stationary and rotating frame of reference.

Figure 3.34: Multiple frames of reference

Figure 3.35: Settings for MFR and interface

Step 10: Two periodic interfaces were created as shown.

Figure 3.36: Periodic interfaces

Step 11: After assigning all the boundaries, the CFX solver was selected from the object tree to complete the simulation.

A number of simulations were carried at different published TSR values for turbines in the velocity range of 3 to 5 m/s. This velocity range was selected based on the roof top anemometer reading.

Figure 3.37: Selection of solver and settings for the simulation

In CFD post, the torque on one blade was estimated using function calculator. Further the performance of the turbine for the site specific conditions were calculated.

3.8 Summary:

This chapter presents in details of for modeling a site to estimate the wind velocity and turbulence intensity using CFX (ANSYS).The details of geometrical modeling and estimation of the input parameters for simulation was also explained. The chapter further interpreted the various steps involved in meshing and selection of boundary condition to run a turbine simulation. The obtained result is given in the next chapter.

Chapter 4: Results

This chapter presents the results of work carried in chapter 3 including the graphical representation of wind profile at the meteorological stations and the site. The CFD simulation results have been presented in pictorial and graphical form for the better understanding of the complex flow field at the site. The turbine output has been estimated for the observed site velocity and the electrical power has been represented graphically at different roof top locations.

4.1. The velocity profile obtained at the site and meteorological station in Dublin:

Ideally, the wind velocity is represented by a logarithmic profile; the mean velocity has been plotted against the elevation at the meteorological station and at the site to see the variation of wind velocity at the two locations. The roof top anemometer wind data has been used to plot the graph at the site. The wind profile at the site can be in figure 4.1. As seen from the graph, the velocity is defined poorly up to a height of 10 m and also above this height it can be seen from the graph that the wind speed is increasing with the elevation but the variation is neither logarithmic nor exponential. Additionally the mean wind profile at the meteorological station has been plotted as shown in figure 4.2. The curve is smooth because of the open area with grass which makes the roughness length zero hence, resulting into an ideal logarithmic wind profile. Due to this reason these meteorological station data are used as a reference for evaluating the wind variation in a particular locality.

Figure 4.1: Mean wind profile (a) at the site upto 50 m and (b) at Dublin meteorological station upto 240 m

4.2. Probabilistic analysis of wind data:

As the wind is variable and inconsistent in urban areas, it is important to carry the probabilistic analysis for defining the wind variability within a confidence interval. The Weibull curve has been plotted with a shape factor of 2.12 and a scale factor of 2.85 m/s. The purpose of the assessment is electricity generation using turbines, thus the curve was plotted in the range of 3 m/s to 15 m/s according to the values given by the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI). From the Weibull plot it is inferred that 73 % of the time, the wind entering Dublin city is suitable for the power generation.

Figure 4.2: Weibull distribution plot at Dublin Airport

As seen in section 4.1, the wind characteristics at site are different from the wind characteristics at the meteorological stations. Thus the Weibull probability distribution function at the site using the meteorological station wind data was plotted with the estimated shape factor of 2.12 and a scale factor is 4.33 m/s. The results obtained shows that only 63% of the time wind at the roof top is suitable for micro generation.

Figure 4.3: Weibull distribution plot for the predicted wind speed at the site

The Weibull distribution was then plotted using the roof top weather station data. The shape and scale factor used was 1.39 and 2.85 m/s respectively. The plot shows that 32 % of the time wind at the site is suitable for electricity generation, which is half of the value obtained earlier.

Figure 4.4: Weibull distribution plot for the observed wind speed at the site

Analyzing the three Weibull plots above, it can be inferred that although Weibull plot gives a more realistic estimation of the wind conditions, site measurements are required for evaluating the on-site wind resources. In case the site measurements are unavailable, the geometrically detailed information of the roughness elements can be used improve the accuracy of the result. Predicted velocity is the velocity obtained from meteorological wind by applying the Oke's roughness classification.

4.3. Directional variation of the wind:

Measurement of the wind velocity includes wind speed and direction to estimate the directional variability of wind in Dublin. The wind rose plot at Dublin airport, Casement aerodrome and at the site is given below. From the wind rose plots, the directional effect of surface roughness from each direction can be approximated. For example, comparing the wind rose of Dublin airport and Roebuck Residence it can be inferred that the built environment (surface roughness) present

in the south east direction are denser. Hence wind coming from that direction reduces further in its magnitude. Looking at the wind rose plot of Casement aerodrome, the effect of Dublin mountain on its south east can be seen clearly giving uniform wind speed from that direction (as the presence of mountain dominates over all the effects) . The monthly wind rose plot for Dublin airport has been attached in appendix A.

Figure 4.5: Wind rose plot at Dublin airport

Figure 4.6: Wind rose plot at Casement aerodrome

Figure 4.7: Wind Rose plot at site

4.4. Results from CFD simulation:

CFD is a complex tool for analysis in terms of evaluating its reliability; even for many professionals it seems challenging. A solution is termed as reliable when convergence is reached; convergence is achieved when change in variables from one iteration to the next is negligible. At the convergence overall property conservation is achieved, the imbalances are measured in terms of residuals. In section 3.8 the residuals value was established to be 10^{-5} , the mass residuals has been shown below.

Figure 4.8: Plot showing the solution residuals once the run is over

4.4.1. Normalized velocity contour:

The feasibility of wind turbines in urban areas depends on the proper understanding of the wind flow patterns. The wind velocity at the site was normalized with free stream velocity expressed as dimensionless velocity ratios, the inlet mass flow rate was taken as the free stream velocity (U_{∞}) and contours were plotted. Normalized velocity ($\frac{U}{U_{\infty}}$) contour has been plotted, the contour has value greater than one (>1) at 40 m above the ground as shown in figure 4.10 (b), the value increases to 1.12 at a height of 120 m above the ground (100 m above the roof). The normalized velocity contour showed maximum value of 0.85 between 0.3 m to 0.5 m above the roof top, above 0.5 m to 1.5 m the normalized velocity was 0.83 and above 1.5 m the value was 0.84 m, at 2 m above the roof top the velocity ratios varies between (0.46-0.82) as shown in figure 4.10 (b).

Figure 4.9: (a) Normalized velocity contour plot at a height of (a) 2 m and (b) at 40 m above the roof top

Looking at the Warwick trials reports it was considered that the feasible height would be 3 m above the roof top for the placement of turbine, hence the detailed exploration of wind was done from 1 m above the roof top to 3 m above the roof top. Here 1 m was selected as the minimum height for the turbine placement considering the micro turbine diameter range between (300 mm – 500 mm) and the minimum clearance for the turbine rotor was 0.5 m above the roof top.

4.4.2. Power in the wind:

As shown in chapter 2, high wind velocity and area of the turbine are the important criterion which decides the power obtained through a turbine (assuming the density of air constant). Thus a variable named (variable 4) has been defined as power per unit area in CFX post process as represented in equation below:

$$variable4 = \frac{1}{2} * (1.2 \left[\frac{kg}{m^3} \right]) * (velocity)^3 \quad (4.1)$$

Figure 4.10: Contour plot of variable 4 at 1 m above the roof top.

For precise analysis four lines have been selected on the two roof top as shown in figure above and graphs have been plotted at different heights. To compare the variation on building along the length graphs have plotted for line and 2 in one graph and line 3 and 4 in another graph

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.11: Graphs representing the variation of TI at 3 m above the roof top across the length of (a) line 1 and line 2 (b) line 3 and line 4

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.12: Graphs representing the variation of TI at 2m above the roof top across the length of (a) line 1 and line 2 (b) line 3 and line 4

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.13: Graphs representing the variation of variable 4 at 3 m above the roof top across the length of (a) line 1 and line 2 (b) line 3 and line 4

4.4.3 Turbulent Intensity:

In Urban areas presence of dense man-made structures (blunt bodies) leading to impinging in front of the building, separation at the edges and vortex shedding makes the wind flow pattern chaotic or turbulent. The turbulence is a flow characteristic statistically which is measured in terms of turbulence intensity (TI), which is defined as the continuous random motion of the air, which are superimposed on the average wind velocity and expressed in equation 3.6. In order to calculate TI a variable MYTI was defined as shown in equation 4.2. This variable has been plotted along the length of line 1, 2, 3 and four as shown in figure

$$MYTI = \frac{u_{rms}}{U} \quad (4.2)$$

Here u_{rms} is the Standard Deviation, of the turbulent velocity fluctuations at a particular location over a specified period of time. U is the average of velocity at the same location over same time period. Turbulence affects the power performance of the turbines which includes fatigue wake effects, and noise effects the power performance of the turbines which includes fatigue, wake effects, and noise becomes very important for the smaller turbines which is likely the cause of fatigue in the blades of the turbine and makes them nonfunctional. For the precise analysis the variation has been plotted along the four selected line as shown in figure 4.10 and the graphs at different elevation is presented below.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.14: Graphs representing the variation of TI at 1m above the roof top across the length of (a) line 1 and line 2 (b) line 3 and line 4

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.15: Graphs representing the variation of TI at 2 m above the roof top across the length of (a) line 1 and line 2 (b) line 3 and line 4

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.16: Graphs representing the variation of TI at 3 m above the roof top across the length of (a) line 1 and line 2 (b) line 3 and line 4

4.4.4 Vortices between the buildings:

The wind velocity is very low just above the ground and between the buildings. It can be seen clearly that the air particle gains momentum as they rise from the ground, the red contours shows the layer with the highest velocity. Hence to obtain the maximum energy from the wind the best

option is to mount the turbine at a height of 120m above the roof top, which is not viable. The wind resource is comparatively very less in the zone of interest for RIWTs, which is represented by light blue and light green. To explore the zone of interest closely, planes were selected and the velocity streamlines were plotted at different elevations.

a) At an elevation of 5 m

b) At an elevation of 15 m

c) At an elevation of 20 m

d) At an elevation of 22 m

Figure 4.17: Figure showing the velocity streamlines plotted at different elevations

From the above figures it can be seen that the vortices formed around the buildings are more prominent at lower heights and starts fading as the elevation increases. It also asserts the theory that the flow disorder (turbulence) decreases with increase in height. At an elevation of 20 m and 22 m the wind velocity is comparatively higher in magnitude. At an elevation of 20 m the wind velocity varies from 0.4 m/s to 4 m/s and at an elevation of 22 m the variation is from 0.63 m/s to 4.26 m/s.

Also from the table and figure it can be seen that at the roof top of RR four different points were selected. At each point the velocity varies and therefore the power. Thus optimizing the location can increase the power output by a factor of 4 (point 4, point1). The Wall shear on the building walls was plotted to see the various turbulence zone so that the zone of flow separation can be avoided. In blunt body (like buildings) aerodynamics these are commonly occurring phenomenon and their locations must be avoided for the proper functioning of a turbine.

Figure 4.18: Plot of wall shear on the building walls

Looking at the wall shear of the building and the velocity contour in figure 4.9, it is clearly observed that the wind velocities are more consistent at the center of the roof and the building edges should be avoided.

4.5. Location selected for turbine installation:

In order to harness the available wind resource in the roof zone 10 locations on different roof tops were selected as shown below and the velocity at each selected points was estimated. The power generated by a turbine of 400 mm diameter ($C_p = 0.25$) has been presented in the table below:

Figure 4.19: Figure showing the selected 10 points on different roof tops

Table 4.1: Table showing the power generated at the ten different locations

Points selected	Estimated Power (watt)	Velocity(m/s)
Point 1	0.52	2.677
Point 2	1.129	3.45514
Point 3	0.59	2.776
Point4	0.28	2.1771
Point5	1.42	3.72501
Point 6	1.209	3.53846
Point7	0.918	3.22096
Point8	0.03	0.920524
Point 9	0.038	1.11761
Point 10	0.038	1.11761

Figure 4.20:3D visualization for the turbine placed on RR roof top at location 4

4.5.1. CFD results for wind turbine:

For a rotating domain around an axis CFX solver computes the appropriate Coriolis and centrifugal momentum term, and solves a rotating frame total energy equation. The total force and total torque has been monitored for estimating the convergence. The y-axis represents the number of time steps and the x-axis represents the magnitude of the total force and the torque acting on one blade of the turbine used for the simulation. The other convergence graphs have been shown in the appendix.

Table 4.2: Table showing the torques generated for different rotation speeds of turbine

Turbine diameter	Normal Velocity(m/s)	TSR	Rotation second	Torque generated by one blade [N-m]
400mm	3	4	9.5	0.0004037
		3.5	8.35	0.0003957
		3.0	7.165	0.00386944
		2.5	4.8	0.0037256
		4	10,03	0.00040769
	4	4	12.73	0.000712016
		3	11.146	0.0005022
	5	4.5	9.55	0.00068123
		3.5	15.92	0.0011064

As shown in the table the turbine torque is still increasing. Hence higher values of wind speed are needed to obtain the power curve for the turbine but the wind speed at the site varies between 0-8 m/s.

4.5.2. Qualitative results for the turbine:

The vector field at wind turbine has been plotted below which also shows that the mesh was accurate and efficient for reducing the systematic error. The velocity vortex of the core region has been shown below. It can be seen that the tip of the turbine blade is rotating at three times the speed of the rotor.

Figure 4.21: The velocity variation in the vortex core

4.6. Summary:

This chapter presented the various quantities selected for the estimating roof top wind resources. It has been observed the roof top wind resources was varying significantly .The reliability results have been validated in the in chapter5 provide detailed information for estimating the available wind resource at the selected site. These results have been explored further in chapter 6 and a discussion has been made regarding the robustness of the approach adopted.

Chapter 5: Discussions

This first section of the chapter presents the critical analyses of the results presented in chapter 4 in the light of previous work done. Some of the works carried in the past are very basic still significant and relevant to the work carried presently. For instance, the work carried by Abohela (2012) studied the aerodynamics of different roof shapes as discussed in 2.8. The section of the paper discusses the reliability of the CFD results comparing it with the work done in past work by Richard and Hoxly which has formed a foundation for controlling the errors in results to an extent, which are validated

5.1 Comparisons of the wind data at two meteorological stations:

The wind data of two Dublin meteorological stations were plotted to assess the characteristics of wind entering Dublin city and how it changes on its interaction with built environment. The mean wind profile at the two meteorological stations is as shown in figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Comparison of mean wind speed between Casement Aerodrome and Dublin Airport

As visible from the graph the mean wind speed at Casement aerodrome lags behind the mean wind velocity obtained at the airport. The reason for this was investigated and it was found that the proximity of Dublin Mountains to the Casement aerodrome leads to the lag due to the sheltering effect, whereas Dublin airport receives an unobstructed flow due to its proximity to the ocean. Thus, before using the data from any meteorological station it is always advisable to get the knowledge about the local topography. For Dublin it is arguably more accurate to consider the Dublin airport wind data as a reference. The graph also depicts that at a height of 50m-60m, the variation of mean wind speed is comparatively less, afterwards the lag increases with the height. The average height of Dublin Mountains is 1120 m; therefore the velocity profile was plotted upto a height of 1400m. Once the wind profile at the meteorological stations were plotted, it was important to estimate the wind profile at the site. For plotting the wind profile at the site the time series data recorded at the roof top weather station was used. The graph below shows the difference between the wind profile at the site and the airport.

Figure 5.2: Graph showing the difference in mean wind profile at RR and Dublin airport

As seen in the graph the wind speed at the site is approximately three times less than the wind speed at the airport. It means that the wind loses its kinetic energy significantly while entering into the city. Hence the power prediction for any specific area based on the meteorological wind data gives an overestimated value of power generated. This is because of the fact that the meteorological stations were installed in accordance with the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) guidelines for the open exposure condition (Instruments and observing methods, Report no 55), whereas the site under consideration has dense built environment.

For evaluating the wind resource at the site, the meteorological wind data was extrapolated using the land roughness classification criterion shown in table 3.2. The graph showing the comparison between the predicted wind speed and the observed wind speed at the roof top is presented in figure 5.3.

Figure 5.3: Comparison of wind power curve generated by the estimated mean wind velocity at the roof top and the predicted mean wind velocity obtained by the meteorological data

From the graph, it is seen that the Oke's roughness classification overestimates the wind speed at the roof top by a factor of 20%. Both the wind profile plots intersect at an elevation of 12m which is the average building height at the site, at this height the estimated speed is less than the predicted speed.

5.2. Use of Weibull function for wind power estimation method:

In the absence of field measurement the accurate estimation of the wind velocity at a location is not possible unless details of the aerodynamic parameters at the site are available. The Oke's roughness criteria overestimated the wind velocity at the site by 20% as seen earlier. A method was devised which used the Weibull probability function values along with the time series data for the estimation of power from a turbine of known capacity factor. The steps followed are mentioned below:

The probability for a particular wind speed is given by:

$$F(u) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{u}{c}\right)^k\right) \quad (5.1)$$

Here $F(u)$ is the fraction of time for which the hourly mean wind speed exceeds U , c and k are the scale and shape parameters as described in chapter 2. For any particular range of velocity the $F(U)$ calculated was almost equal value for both the observed velocity and the predicted velocity. Observed velocity is the velocity observed by the anemometer at the roof top and predicted velocity is the velocity obtained from meteorological wind data by applying Oke's roughness classification. The available power in the wind was calculated using equation 4.2. The graph plotted is shown below:

$$P = \frac{1}{2}AU^3F(u) \quad (5.2)$$

Where P is the available power (W), A is rotor swept area (m^2), and U is the mean wind velocity (m/s).

From the graph it can be inferred that even if the wind measurement at the site was not available, the power at the site was estimated accurately by carefully choosing the value of surface roughness within the range. This coinciding values of power also asserted that Oke's parameters

selected by iteration were correct and represented the site specific aerodynamic characteristics in the best possible way.

5.3. Robustness of the devised method as power estimation tool:

The two main reasons for poor performance of a turbine in urban areas are:

- a) Turbine design does not account for the complex nature of flow in urban areas
- b) Difficulty in estimating the available wind resource (Drew et.al, 2013).

Therefore a novel method has been devised in the current work to estimate the extractable wind power for a given velocity resource at the site.

The steps carried for the power estimation at the site are:

- Selection of optimized Oke's roughness parameters
- Estimation of velocity at the turbine height
- Finding the Weibull parameter
- Exploring the wind flow field at turbine location using CFD
- Finding the location for maximum velocity
- Calculating the probability of occurrence for the maximum velocity
- Calculate the power generated from the turbine at maximum velocity
- Multiply the obtained power by the probability of occurrence.

The above presented steps have been varied for the four locations selected on the RR roof top and the graph has been plotted as shown in figure 5.3. The graph has been validated by using the roof top weather station data

5.4. Reliability of CFD Results:

CFD is a complex tool for analysis in terms of evaluating its reliability; even for many professionals it seems challenging. It was seen in section 4.5.2 and 4.5.3 that the roof top resources were varying in both lateral and longitudinal direction to a significant extent. Thus to prove that it was solely due to the wind plow pattern at the site not because of the error in

simulating the wind profile, three line have been selected as shown in figure 5.4. Velocity, turbulent kinetin energy (TKE) and turbulent eddy dissipation (TED) have been plotted as discussed by Blocken et.al(2007)

Figure 5.4: Three lines selected to verify the homogeneity of inlet flow

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5.5: Graphs showing the variation of (a) TED, (b) TKE and (c) velocity along line 2, line 3 and line 19

Looking at these graphs it can be observed that the wind flow along the three lines were symmetrical with slight deviation. It is now verified that there was insignificant error due to the inhomogeneity of the approach flow. Hence the results obtained can be trusted.

5.5. Validation using literature:

Formation of vortices are one of the most common features of building aerodynamics. CFD results has been post processed to visualize the vortices formed at the site. The vortices obtained at the site has been compared with the work carried by Abohela (2012) studied the aerodynamics of different roof shapes as discussed in section 2.8.

a) Vortices formed at the site on the back of RR b) Vortices formed behind a generic rectangular structure

Figure 5.6: Vortices formed around the building due the bluff body aerodynamics

In both the figures, the basic nature of the flow is similar.

- In the previous studies, a generic rectangular building model has been used and the flow direction was normal to the façade. The reattachment length occurred at $1.60H$ (height of the cube).

In the current study, a group of buildings have been simulated. These are not perfectly cube shaped buildings and the reattachment length is $7H$ away from the leeward façade .

It can be inferred that as the height of the building and the number of buildings increases the dimension of the leeward vortex, which means that the flow reattachment length increases. These vortices are transient in nature, thus it is difficult to define this complex chaotic phenomenon using any physical law.

Ledo et al.(2011) described a rule of thumb based on the flow separation location for the flat and pyramidal roof and asserted that on flat roof, all the three positions (edge, centre and corner) can be considered for the estimation of velocity.

The RR is a flat roof building but the building plan is not an ideal rectangular or square. The velocity is highest near the location selected at east edge of the building which is point 4. This location has a high wind potential which can be verified by looking into the wind rose plot at RR.

Therefore these study results can be very generic in their nature and the conditions at the real site depend on various factors like the building orientation to the flow direction, the outline of the building shape, and the wind direction.

5.6. Measurement points selected between the building groups:

Four measurements points have been selected on the site at an elevation of 22m (approximate hub height for a RIWT rotor) and the velocity has been estimated and compared with the velocities estimated on the adjacent roof top (located by red polygons) to find how the wind behaved locally due to the presence of these structures nearby.

Figure 5.7: Velocity measured at roof top and points and the positions on adjacent roof top for velocity measurement

Table 5.1: Table showing the velocities measured at location points and adjacent roof top

Measurements location	Velocity at located points(m/s)	Velocity at adjacent roof (m/s)
1	2.8	2.677
2	3.273	3.22
3	3.633	2.177
4	3.303	2.67

The yellow cross hair represents the velocity measurement points (at rooftop elevation) and the red dots represent the points on the roof top. The yellow crosshairs have higher values than the adjacent roof top positions represented by red dots, which shows that the presence of these buildings decelerates the wind, whereas Blackmore (2010) established that the presence of isolated buildings accelerated the wind flow. The study conducted by Blackmore was generic for an open area where the presence of a building accelerated the flow and the velocity estimated on the roof top is higher than the velocity adjacent to the building at the same elevation.

5.6.1. Velocity measurements for a Pyramidal roof:

The work carried by Ledo et al(2011) for a suburban setting states that the roof centre of a pyramidal is not a desirable position for installing a turbine. This outcome contradicts the ideal theory of the wind flow which states that the velocity of wind increases with rise in elevation. The site under study has a pyramidal roof and the velocity has been measured at the three locations shown below.

Figure 5.8: Pyramidal roof with the points selected for study

Table 5.2: Table showing the velocity measured on the pyramidal roof

Location on pyramidal roof top	Velocity (m/s)
Location 1 (roof center)	0.918
Location2 (roof edge)	1.962
Location 3 (roof corner)	1.595

5.7. Summary:

From the discussion it can be assured that the strategy adopted for the computational modelling was rational .It reinforces the fact that in urban boundary layer the flow is complex and its complexity depends on the geometry of the surrounding, where the wind flow is being assessed.

Chapter 6: Future Work and Conclusion

This chapter outlines the limitations, the future work and the conclusions of the work carried out.

6.1. Conclusion:

This study presented a approach for the estimation of available wind power at urban site, the strategy used for the geometrical modelling was a novel in terms of using LIDAR. It is very efficient tool in capturing the site details (Trees, buildings, ground topography) on a larger scale or city scale. Meteorological station wind data was used to calculate the required input parameters Although in the absence of detail land use pattern, it can only give an approximate value. The turbine model used in the study was a generic NREL model, which gave an estimate of the torque produced by the .The obtained CFD result was verified using literature available. The wind above the roof top is highly variable in all the three direction (x,y,z) in terms of velocity and turbulence intensity . Thus it is very much essential to have a precise analysis of at a site, to produce substantial amount of electricity by optimizing the placement location. Looking at the power per unit area for cities like Dublin Ireland definitely RIWT can be considered as an option of green energy .The results obtained gives a basic insight for the turbine placement over some institutional building , which can be used by the manufacture to gain primitive idea about the placement location . This insight will further increase the consumer trust in micro-turbines, leading to wider adaptation and an increase in the cost benefit ratio

Findings of the project:

1. Onsite wind near to the rooftops (from 0.3m to 3m) varies to its extent at the same elevation.
2. At site RIWT can be placed 3.5 meters above the RR roof top to obtain power ranging (220-280)Watt /m².
3. The roof top wind variation depends on the geometry (cubical, cuboidal) of the building and direction of the flow.
4. LIDAR generated point cloud can give geometrically efficient model for CFD, in terms of capturing the orientation of the building with its environs.

5. The optimization of the turbine seating positions before hand is very important, as at some positions close to roof turbine output can be zero. Additionally it can increase the cost benefit ratio for micro turbines.
6. The torque produced by the micro turbines is significantly low so there is no discomfort to the occupant.

6.2. Limitations of the work:

The limitations of the work are:

- a) Due to time constraint mesh independent study was not conducted.
- b) The CFD simulation results were not validated with the field measurement or wind tunnel experiment validation was done only for the velocity at one location due to the time constraints.
- c) The anemometer placed at the site was very close to the roof top .

6.3. Future work:

The work carried out at the site can be extended further by two steps:

- a) Validation of the result and quantification of the error though field study or wind tunnel.
- b) SST k-omega turbulence model can be compared with the obtained K-epsilon model results, to find which turbulence model gives realistic results for roof top wind resources.
- c) Simulating the turbine performance as actuator disc model different location using CFD to estimate the power variation at these locations.

References:

- 1) Kutzbach, J., "Investigations of the modifications of wind profiles by artificially controlled surface roughness". *M.S. thesis, Department of Meteorology, University of Wisconsin-Madison*, (1961):58.
- 2) Lettau, H., "Note on aerodynamic roughness-parameter estimation on the basis of roughness-element description." *J.Appl. Meteor.*, (1969):8:828–32.
- 3) Counihan, J., "Wind tunnel determination of the roughness length as a function of fetch and density of three-dimensional roughness element." *Atmos. Environ.*, (1971):5: 637–42.
- 4) Jackson, P.S, and Hunt J.C.R., "Turbulent Wind Flow over a Low Hill." *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, (1975): 929-55.
- 5) Wieringa, J., "Representativeness of Wind Observations at Airports." *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, (1980):61: 962–971.
- 6) Raupach, M.R., "Drag and Drag Partition on Rough Surfaces." *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, (1992):60:375-395.
- 7) Raupach, M. R., "Simplified expressions for vegetation roughness length and zero-plane displacement as functions of canopy height and area index." *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, (1994):71:211–16
- 8) MacDonald, R. W., Griffiths, R.F, and Hall, D.J., "An improved method for the estimation of surface roughness of obstacle arrays: A comparative study of the land use and built forms of 110 schemes." *Atmos. Environ.*, (1998):32: 1857–64
- 9) Hillring, Bengt and Roland Krieg, "Wind Energy Potential in Southern Sweden— Example of Planning Methodology." *Renewable Energy*, (1998):13.4:471-79.
- 10) Murakami, S., "Overview of Turbulence Models Applied in CWE–1997." *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, (1998): 74-76: 1-24.
- 11) Grimmond, C. S. B., Oke, T. R., "Aerodynamic properties of urban areas derived from analysis of surface form." *Journal of applied meteorology*, (1999): 38(9): 1262-1292.
- 12) Baillard, C., Schmid, C., Zisserman, A. and Fitzgibbon, A., "Automatic line matching and 3D reconstruction of buildings from multiple views", *ISPRS Conference on Automatic Extraction of GIS Objects from Digital Imagery*, (1999):32: 69-80

- 13) Liebowitz D, Criminisi A, Zisserman A., "Creating Architectural Models from Images." *Computer Graphics Forum* 18, (1999):3: 39–50
- 14) Burton, T., *Wind Energy Handbook*, John Wiley & Sons, (2001).
- 15) Mertens, S., "The Energy Yield of Roof Mounted Wind Turbines." *Wind Engineering*, (2003):27.6:507-18.
- 16) Landberg L., Myllerup L., Rathmann O., Petersen E.L., Jorgensen B.H, Badger J., Mortensen N.G., "Wind Resource Estimation—An Overview." *Wind Energy*, (2003): 6: 261-271.
- 17) Gipe, P., *Wind Power*, London, UK, James and James ltd, (2004).
- 18) Kolmogorov V., Zabih R., "What energy functions can be minimized via graph cuts?" *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 26, (2004): 2:147–59.
- 19) Snavely N., Seitz S. M., Szeliski R., "Photo tourism: Exploring Photo Collections in 3D." *ACM Transactions on Graphics* 25, (2006): 3: 835.
- 20) Watson, Simon, David Infield, and Mark Harding, "Predicting the Performance of Small Wind Turbines in the Roof-Top Urban Environment.", 2007
- 21) Blocken, Bert, Ted Stathopoulos, and Jan Carmeliet. "CFD simulation of the atmospheric boundary layer: wall function problems." *Atmospheric environment* 41.2 (2007): 238-252
- 22) Zebedin L., Bauer J., Karner K., Bischof H., "Fusion of Feature- and Area-Based Information for Urban Buildings Modeling from Aerial Imagery.", *In Computer Vision – ECCV 2008*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, (2008): 873–886.
- 23) Blackmore, P., *Siting micro-wind turbines on house roofs*. Watford: BRE, (2008).
- 24) Eriksson, S., Bernhoff, H., and Leijon, M., "Evaluation of Different Turbine Concepts for Wind Power." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 12.5, (2008): 1419-434.
- 25) Holland, Donald E., Judith A. Berglund, Joseph P. Spruce, and Rodney D. Mckellip, "Derivation of Effective Aerodynamic Surface Roughness in Urban Areas from Airborne Lidar Terrain Data." *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, (2008):47.10: 2614-626.
- 26) Groger G., Kolbe T. H., Czerwinski A., Nagel C., "OpenGIS city geography markup language (CityGML) encoding standard." *Open Geospatial Consortium Inc. Reference number of this OGC{ntextregistered} project document: OGC* (2008).

- 27) Xie, Z. & Castro, I. P., "Large-eddy simulation for flow and dispersion in urban streets." *Atmospheric Environment*, (2009);43: 2174-2185.
- 28) Blackmore, P., *Building-mounted micro-wind turbines on high-rise and commercial buildings*. Watford: BRE, (2010).
- 29) Vanegas C. A., Aliaga D. G., Wonka P., Muller P., Waddell P. A., Watson B., "Modelling the Appearance and Behaviour of Urban Spaces." *Computer Graphics Forum 29*, (2010):1:25–42.
- 30) Kalmikov A. et al., "Wind Power Resource Assessment in Complex Urban Environments: MIT Campus Case-Study Using CFD Analysis," *American Wind Energy Association WINDPOWER 2010 Conference, WEPA, MIT*, (2010).
- 31) Campbell J. B., Wynne R. H., "Introduction to Remote Sensing", *Fifth Edition. Guilford Publications*, 2011.
- 32) Walker, S. L., "Building Mounted Wind Turbines and Their Suitability for the Urban Scale—A Review of Methods of Estimating Urban Wind Resource." *Energy and Buildings*, (2011);43.8:1852-862
- 33) Poullis C., You S., "3D Reconstruction of Urban Areas". *International Conference on 3D Imaging, Modeling, Processing, Visualization and Transmission*, (2011): 33–40
- 34) Ledo, L., Kosasih, P. B. and Cooper, P., "Roof mounting site analysis for micro-wind turbines", *Renewable Energy*, (2011);36.5:1379-391
- 35) Huang, H., Brenner, C. and Sester, M., "3D building roof reconstruction from point clouds via generative models", *Proceedings of the 19th ACM SIGSPATIAL International Conference on Advances in Geographic Information Systems*, (2011):16-24.
- 36) Abohela, Islam, Neveen Hamza, Steven Dudek, "Effect of roof shape on energy yield and positioning of roof mounted wind turbines", *Proceedings of 12th Conference of International Building Performance Simulation Association, Sydney* (2011):14-16
- 37) Thoen, Bill., "Origins of the Compass Rose." *GISNet*, (2011)
- 38) Milanese, Marco, Arturo De Risi, and Domenico Laforgia, "Performance Optimization of Building Integrated-Mounted Wind Turbine." *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, (2012): 69-76.

- 39) Tack, Frederik, Rudi Goossens, and Gurcan Buyuksalih, "Assessment of a Photogrammetric Approach for Urban DSM Extraction from Tri-Stereoscopic Satellite Imagery." *The Photogrammetric Record*, (2012):27.139:293-310.
- 40) Abohela, Islam, Steven Dudek, and Neveen Hamza, "Roof Mounted Wind Turbines: The Influence of Roof Shape, Building Height and Urban Location on Wind Speed." *PLEA2012-28th Conference, Opportunities, Limits & Needs Towards an Environmentally Responsible Architecture Lima, Peru* (2012)
- 41) Dymock, Ben, and Stephen Dance, "Building Integrated Wind Turbines—A Pilot Study." *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, (2013):133.5: 3450.
- 42) Millward-Hopkins, J.T., Tomlin, A.S., Ma L., Ingham, D.B and Pourkashanian, M., "Mapping the Wind Resource over UK Cities." *Renewable Energy*, (2013):55: 202-11.
- 43) Khayrullina, A, Hooff Van T, and Blocken B., "A Study on the Wind Energy Potential in Passages between Parallel Buildings." *6th European and African Conference on Wind Engineering* (2013)
- 44) Gagliano, Antonio, Francesco Nocera, Francesco Patania, and Alfonso Capizzi, "Assessment of Micro-wind Turbines Performance in the Urban Environments: An Aided Methodology through Geographical Information Systems." *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering* (2013):4.1:43
- 45) Drew, D.R., Barlow J.F, and Cockerill, T.T, "Estimating the Potential Yield of Small Wind Turbines in Urban Areas: A Case Study for Greater London, UK." *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* (2013):115: 104-11.
- 46) Singh, Surendra Pal, Kamal Jain, Ravibabu Mandla, V, "Virtual 3D city modeling and techniques", *ISPRS 8th 3DGeoInfo Conference & WG II/2 Workshop*, Istanbul, Turkey, (2013).
- 47) McClune, A.P, Miller P.E., Mills J.P., and Holland D., "Automatic Urban 3D Building Reconstruction from Multi-Ray Photogrammetry." *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences XL.3* (2014): 219-26.
- 48) Toparlar, Y., Blocken B., Vos, P., Van Heijst G.J.F, Janssen W.D, Van Hooff T., Montazeri, H., and Timmermans H.J.P, "CFD Simulation and Validation of Urban

Microclimate: A Case Study for Bergpolder Zuid, Rotterdam." *Building and Environment* (2015):83: 79-90.

49) Periodic Report Summary - ROOF-CAPTURE (Innovative Design for Wind EnergyCapture in Urban Environments)

50) www.wikipedia.com

51) www.seai.ie

52) <http://www.warwickwindtrials.org.uk/3.html>

Appendices:

Appendix A: Wind Rose plot of Dublin Airport and Roebuck Residence for the year 2012

A.1) Wind Rose plot of Dublin Airport for the year 2012

Figure A.1.1: January, 2012

Figure A.1.2: February, 2012

Figure A.1.3: March, 2012

Figure A.1.4: April, 2012

Figure A.1.5: May, 2012

Figure A.1.6: June, 2012

Figure A.1.7: July, 2012

Figure A.1.8: August, 2012

Figure A.1.9: September, 2012

Figure A.1.10: October, 2012

Figure A.1.11: November, 2012

Figure A.1.12: December, 2012

A.2) Wind Rose plot of site selected (RR) for the year 2012

Figure A.2.1: January, 2012

Figure 2.1.2: February, 2012

Figure A.2.3: March, 2012

Figure A.2.4: April, 2012

Figure A.2.5: May, 2012

Figure A.2.6: June, 2012

Figure A.2.7: July, 2012

Figure A.2.8: August, 2012

Figure A.2.9: September, 2012

Figure A.2.10: October, 2012

Figure A.2.11: November, 2012

Figure A.2.12: December, 2012

Appendix B: Frequency plot of Dublin Airport and Roebuck Residence for the year 2012

B.1) Frequency plot of Dublin Airport for the year 2012

Figure B.1.1: January, 2012

Figure B.1.2: February, 2012

Figure B.1.3: March, 2012

Figure B.1.4: April, 2012

Figure B.1.5: May, 2012

Figure B.1.6: June, 2012

Figure B.1.7: July, 2012

Figure B.1.8: August, 2012

Figure B.1.9: September, 2012

Figure B.1.10: October, 2012

Figure B.1.11: November, 2012

Figure B.1.12: December, 2012

B.2) Frequency plot of Roebuck Residence for the year 2012

Figure B.2.1: January, 2012

Figure B.2.2: February, 2012

Figure B.2.3: March, 2012

Figure B.2.4: April, 2012

Figure B.2.5: May, 2012

Figure B.2.6: June, 2012

Figure B.2.7: July, 2012

Figure B.2.8: August, 2012

Figure B.2.9: September, 2012

Figure B.2.10: October, 2012

Figure B.2.11: November, 2012

Figure B.2.12: December, 2012

Appendix C: Sample of MINITAB worksheets

23/03/2015 23:20:46

Welcome to Minitab, press F1 for help.

Descriptive Statistics: 10 mtrs, 5mtrs, 15mtrs, 20mtrs, 30mtrs, 40mtrs, ...

Variable	N	N*	Mean	SE Mean	StDev	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3
10 mtrs	17544	0	10.842	0.0408	5.408	0.0000	7.000	10.000	14.000
5mtrs	17544	0	9.5546	0.0360	4.7656	0.0000	6.1687	8.8124	12.3373
15mtrs	17544	0	11.589	0.0436	5.780	0.0000	7.482	10.688	14.964
20mtrs	17544	0	12.130	0.0457	6.050	0.0000	7.831	11.188	15.663
30mtrs	17544	0	12.895	0.0486	6.432	0.0000	8.325	11.893	16.651
40mtrs	17544	0	13.436	0.0506	6.702	0.0000	8.675	12.392	17.349
50mtrs	17544	0	13.847	0.0521	6.906	0.0000	8.940	12.771	17.880
60mtrs	17544	0	14.183	0.0534	7.074	0.0000	9.157	13.081	18.313
80mtrs	17544	0	14.724	0.0554	7.344	0.0000	9.506	13.580	19.012
100mtrs	17544	0	15.134	0.0570	7.549	0.0000	9.771	13.959	19.542
120 mtrs	17544	0	15.470	0.0583	7.716	0.0000	9.988	14.269	19.976
140 mtrs	17544	0	15.769	0.0594	7.865	0.0000	10.181	14.544	20.361
160 mtrs	17544	0	16.011	0.0603	7.986	0.0000	10.337	14.768	20.675
180mtrs	17544	0	16.235	0.0611	8.098	0.0000	10.482	14.974	20.964
200mtrs	17544	0	16.422	0.0618	8.191	0.0000	10.602	15.146	21.205
220mtrs	17544	0	16.609	0.0625	8.284	0.0000	10.723	15.318	21.446
240mtrs	17544	0	16.777	0.0632	8.368	0.0000	10.831	15.473	21.663

Variable	Maximum
10 mtrs	37.000
5mtrs	32.6059
15mtrs	39.547
20mtrs	41.394
30mtrs	44.005
40mtrs	45.852
50mtrs	47.253
60mtrs	48.399
80mtrs	50.246
100mtrs	51.647
120 mtrs	52.793
140 mtrs	53.812
160 mtrs	54.640
180mtrs	55.404
200mtrs	56.041
220mtrs	56.678
240mtrs	57.251

————— **24/04/2015 09:36:16** —————

Welcome to Minitab, press F1 for help.
 Retrieving project from file: '\\Client\H\$\wind data anyalyses\airport wind profile.MPJ'

————— **25/03/2015 00:09:31** —————

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28/03/2015 17:04:02

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Retrieving project from file: '\\Client\G\$\wind data anyalyses\graph near building.MPJ'

30/03/2015 07:53:53

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Retrieving project from file: '\\Client\H\$\wind data anyalyses\graph near building.MPJ'

Descriptive Statistics: 28mtrs, 50mtrs, 55mtrs, 60mtrs

Variable	N	N*	Mean	SE Mean	StDev	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3
28mtrs	13611	3843	3.1597	0.0182	2.1280	-0.0119	1.5567	2.7548	4.3534
50mtrs	13611	3843	4.5478	0.0238	2.7771	0.1158	2.4564	4.0322	6.1470
55mtrs	13611	3843	4.7583	0.0247	2.8773	0.1352	2.5919	4.2265	6.4274
60mtrs	13611	3843	4.9474	0.0254	2.9676	0.1526	2.7177	4.4005	6.6784

Variable	Maximum
28mtrs	14.8736
50mtrs	19.4289
55mtrs	20.1258
60mtrs	20.7522

Descriptive Statistics: 28mtrs, 50mtrs, 55mtrs, 60mtrs

Variable	N	N*	Mean	SE Mean	StDev	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3
28mtrs	13611	3843	3.1597	0.0182	2.1280	-0.0119	1.5567	2.7548	4.3534
50mtrs	13611	3843	4.5478	0.0238	2.7771	0.1158	2.4564	4.0322	6.1470
55mtrs	13611	3843	4.7583	0.0247	2.8773	0.1352	2.5919	4.2265	6.4274
60mtrs	13611	3843	4.9474	0.0254	2.9676	0.1526	2.7177	4.4005	6.6784

Variable	Maximum
28mtrs	14.8736
50mtrs	19.4289
55mtrs	20.1258
60mtrs	20.7522

Descriptive Statistics: 10mtrs

Variable	N	N*	Mean	SE Mean	StDev	Minimum	Q1	Median
10mtrs	13611	3843	-1.1482	0.00751	0.8762	-5.4625	-1.6639	-1.0978

Variable	Q3	Maximum
10mtrs	-0.6068	3.4843

30/03/2015 08:19:52

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Descriptive Statistics: 30mtrs

Variable	N	N*	Mean	SE Mean	StDev	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3
30mtrs	17544	0	5.2252	0.0197	2.6062	0.0000	3.3735	4.8193	6.7470

Variable	Maximum
30mtrs	17.8313

Descriptive Statistics: 30mtrs_1

Variable	N	N*	Mean	SE Mean	StDev	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3
30mtrs_1	17544	0	4.6653	0.0176	2.3269	0.0000	3.0120	4.3029	6.0241

Variable	Maximum
30mtrs_1	15.9208

31/03/2015 16:33:00

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Scatterplot of height vs power1, power predicted

06/04/2015 15:41:49

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Retrieving project from file: '\\Client\G\$\wind data analyses\okes formula validation.MPJ'

Distribution Identification for predicted velocity

- * NOTE * Cannot fit the following distribution(s) because data contain non-positive values: Exponential, Lognormal, Weibull, Gamma, Loglogistic
- * NOTE * Cannot perform Box-Cox transformation because data contain non-positive values.
- * NOTE * P Value for original data > 0.1. No Johnson transformation function is selected.

3-Parameter Lognormal

- * WARNING * Newton-Raphson algorithm has not converged after 100 iterations.
- * WARNING * Convergence has not been reached for the parameter estimates criterion.

2-Parameter Exponential

- * WARNING * Variance/Covariance matrix of estimated parameters does not exist. The threshold parameter is assumed fixed when calculating confidence intervals.

3-Parameter Weibull

- * WARNING * Newton-Raphson algorithm has not converged after 100 iterations.
- * WARNING * Convergence has not been reached for the log-likelihood criterion.
- * WARNING * Convergence has not been reached for the parameter estimates criterion.

3-Parameter Gamma

- * WARNING * Newton-Raphson algorithm has not converged after 100 iterations.
- * WARNING * Convergence has not been reached for the parameter estimates criterion.
- * WARNING * Variance/Covariance matrix of estimated parameters does not exist. The threshold parameter is assumed fixed when calculating confidence intervals.

3-Parameter Loglogistic

- * WARNING * Newton-Raphson algorithm has not converged after 100 iterations.
- * WARNING * Convergence has not been reached for the log-likelihood criterion.
- * WARNING * Convergence has not been reached for the parameter estimates criterion.

Distribution ID Plot for predicted velocity

Descriptive Statistics

N	N*	Mean	StDev	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
19	0	3.62478	2.03864	4.06	0	6.27	-0.634056	-0.657472

Goodness of Fit Test

Distribution	AD	P
Normal	0.488	0.196
3-Parameter Lognormal	0.520	*
2-Parameter Exponential	2.013	<0.010
3-Parameter Weibull	0.245	>0.500
Smallest Extreme Value	0.243	>0.250
Largest Extreme Value	0.922	0.017
3-Parameter Gamma	1.105	*
Logistic	0.434	0.235
3-Parameter Loglogistic	0.437	*

ML Estimates of Distribution Parameters

Distribution	Location	Shape	Scale	Threshold
Normal*	3.62478		2.03864	
3-Parameter Lognormal	6.50619		0.00297	-665.64625
2-Parameter Exponential			3.82615	-0.20138
3-Parameter Weibull		375.53689	585.43409	-580.88458
Smallest Extreme Value	4.55115		1.55692	
Largest Extreme Value	2.58246		2.05173	
3-Parameter Gamma		452.71131	0.09420	-39.40126
Logistic	3.80313		1.16082	
3-Parameter Loglogistic	6.49288		0.00176	-656.61932

* Scale: Adjusted ML estimate

Distribution Identification for 22mtrs

- * NOTE * Cannot fit the following distribution(s) because data contain non-positive values: Exponential, Lognormal, Weibull, Gamma, Loglogistic
- * NOTE * Cannot perform Box-Cox transformation because data contain non-positive values.
- * NOTE * Fail to select a Johnson transformation function with P-Value > 0.1. No transformation is made.

2-Parameter Exponential

- * WARNING * Variance/Covariance matrix of estimated parameters does not exist. The threshold parameter is assumed fixed when calculating confidence intervals.

27/03/2015 19:48:04

Welcome to Minitab, press F1 for help.

Distribution Identification for Wind Speed

- * NOTE * Cannot fit the following distribution(s) because data contain non-positive values: Exponential, Lognormal, Weibull, Gamma,

Loglogistic

* NOTE * Cannot perform Box-Cox transformation because data contain non-positive values.

* NOTE * Fail to select a Johnson transformation function with P-Value > 0.1. No transformation is made.

2-Parameter Exponential

* WARNING * Variance/Covariance matrix of estimated parameters does not exist. The threshold parameter is assumed fixed when calculating confidence intervals.

Distribution ID Plot for Wind Speed

Descriptive Statistics

N	N*	Mean	StDev	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
17544	0	10.8422	5.40782	10	0	37	0.691745	0.496392

Goodness of Fit Test

Distribution	AD	P
Normal	134.048	<0.005
3-Parameter Lognormal	35.421	*
2-Parameter Exponential	1973.091	<0.010
3-Parameter Weibull	33.138	<0.005
Smallest Extreme Value	607.561	<0.010
Largest Extreme Value	44.059	<0.010
3-Parameter Gamma	32.017	*
Logistic	115.572	<0.005
3-Parameter Loglogistic	58.682	*

ML Estimates of Distribution Parameters

Distribution	Location	Shape	Scale	Threshold
Normal*	10.84223		5.40782	
3-Parameter Lognormal	2.90115		0.28352	-8.09486
2-Parameter Exponential			10.84284	-0.00062
3-Parameter Weibull		2.12009	12.29234	-0.03678
Smallest Extreme Value	13.69415		6.30178	
Largest Extreme Value	8.31129		4.47138	
3-Parameter Gamma		5.68408	2.29406	-2.19738
Logistic	10.49104		3.06448	
3-Parameter Loglogistic	2.79540		0.18338	-6.28263

* Scale: Adjusted ML estimate

Probability Plot for Wind Speed

3-Parameter Loglogistic - 95% CI

Goodness of Fit Test

3-Parameter Loglogistic

AD = 58.682

P-Value = *